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Final Study Report

**Impact of EU label changes and revised pregnancy prevention
programme for oral retinoid-containing medicinal products: acitretin,
alitretinoin and isotretinoin**

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Summary information

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Research question and objectives	<p>This report describes a pharmaco-epidemiological study using longitudinal data collected in six electronic health care databases from 4 European Union (EU) countries to investigate the use of oral retinoid-containing medicinal products authorised in the EU before and after implementation of the 2018 revised measures for pregnancy prevention in clinical practice, and effectiveness of the 2018 intervention. The research objectives were:</p> <p>Objective 1: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns of oral retinoid-containing medicinal products in females of childbearing potential, and to investigate whether significant changes in prescribing patterns occurred (pre-/post-intervention).</p> <p>Objective 2: To determine prescribers' compliance with the recommendations in the SmPC for oral retinoid-containing medicinal products, by indication (i.e., dermatological conditions including acne, psoriasis and eczema), by age group, by duration of use, and by database.</p> <p>Objective 3: To determine, in so far as is possible, patients' use of effective contraception in compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for oral retinoid-containing medicinal products, by indication (i.e., dermatological conditions including acne, psoriasis and eczema), by age group, by method of contraception and by database.</p> <p>Objective 4: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns over time for alternative medicines prescribed in females of childbearing potential and females becoming pregnant where oral retinoid-containing medicinal products had previously been prescribed or discontinued, by indication, by age group and by database.</p>

	Objective 5: Based on the results of the above, to estimate the effectiveness of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for oral retinoids.
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Marketing authorisation holder(s)	Not applicable

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1. Abstract

Title

Impact of 2018 EU label changes and revised pregnancy prevention programme for oral retinoid-containing medicinal products (acitretin, alitretinoin and isotretinoin): utilisation and prescribing trends.

Keywords

Oral retinoids, acitretin, alitretinoin, isotretinoin, congenital abnormalities, contraceptive agents, dermatologic conditions, acne, eczema and psoriasis, pregnancy.

Rationale and background

In March 2018, the European pregnancy prevention program (PPP) for oral retinoids was updated. Despite a reduction in number, pregnant women exposed to retinoids have continued to occur, raising concerns about compliance and effectiveness of PPPs in clinical practice. In this context, a pharmaco-epidemiological study was conducted using longitudinal data collected in 6 electronic health care databases from 4 EU countries (Spain, Italy, Netherlands, Denmark) to describe the use of oral retinoid-containing medicinal products authorised in the EU before and after implementation of the 2018 revised measures for pregnancy prevention in clinical practice, and to measure the impact of the 2018 intervention by carrying out an interrupted time series analysis.

1.1 Objective 1

Aim: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns of oral retinoid-containing medicinal products in females of childbearing potential, and to investigate whether significant changes in utilisation and prescribing patterns after the 2018 European Pregnancy Prevention Programme occurred, using longitudinal data collected from six electronic health care databases from different EU countries.

Methods: An observational times series study consisting of females of childbearing age (aged 12 and 55 years) derived from electronic health record data sources in the Netherlands (PHARMO database network), Spain (Base de datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria (BIFAP); Valencia health system integrated database (VID), Italy (ARS Tuscany), Caserta Record Linkage Database (CASERTA), and Denmark (Danish National Registers (DNR)). We estimated the incidence, prevalence and rate of discontinuation of use of oral retinoid-containing medicinal products per month, in each data source. An interrupted time series analysis was performed to assess changes after the implementation of the 2018 PRAC intervention the date could vary by country.

Results: In the study population comprising 11,570,047 women of childbearing age (12-55 years), 88,992 persons used an oral retinoid at any point during the 11 years of the study period. Most persons were below 31 years of age at start of follow-up. The most frequently used retinoid was isotretinoin (95.6%) of all users, followed by acitretin and alitretinoin. Monthly incidence and prevalence rates showed that retinoid prescriptions have a strong seasonal pattern, with decreasing incidence in the summer months, especially in southern countries. This seasonal pattern is aligned with the clinical practice recommendations to be careful with use with sunlight due to potential photosensitivity (Ferguson et al 1989), and potentially different disease severity across seasons. The pre-intervention monthly retinoid discontinuation rate in PHARMO (NL) was 7.0% and the post-intervention one was 7.5%. ARS (IT) showed a pre-intervention average discontinuation rate of 16.2% and 15.9% in the post-intervention period. In Caserta (IT), pre-intervention monthly retinoid discontinuation rate reached 16.5% and the post-intervention rate was 15.3%. Pre- and post-intervention discontinuation percentages for VID (ES) were 10.6% and 12.1% per month, respectively. In BIFAP (ES), monthly discontinuation rates were 25.1% in the pre-intervention period and 18.5% in the post-intervention time.

Conclusion: Prescription/dispensing rates increased slightly over time, but comparison of the incidence or prevalence rates and trends before and after the intervention (excluding COVID-19 years) and discontinuation rates showed no significant change after the RMM implementation in any of the data sources.

1.2 Objective 2

Aim: To determine prescribers' compliance with the recommendations in the SmPC (sections 4.4, 4.6) for oral retinoid-containing medicinal products, by age group and by database, using longitudinal data collected from six electronic health care databases from different EU countries.

Methods: An observational times series study consisting of females of childbearing age (aged 12 and 55 years) derived from electronic health record datasources in the Netherlands (PHARMO database network), Spain (Base de datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria (BIFAP); Valencia health system integrated database (VID), Italy (ARS Tuscany), Caserta Record Linkage Database (CASERTA), and Denmark (Danish National Registers (DNR)), who used an oral retinoid during the study period (2010-2020). First, we estimated the number and proportion of oral retinoid users with a record of a pregnancy test within the 90 days i) before and ii) after the date of retinoid prescribing or dispensing per month. Second, we estimated the number and proportion of retinoid users with a record indicating concomitant use of contraception per month. We estimated the change in level and trend for pregnancy test and contraception proportions after the implementation of the 2018 PRAC intervention through an interrupted time series analysis.

Results: A total of 88,992 women of childbearing age who used an oral retinoid were included in the study-population for these objectives. Danish registries, ARS and Caserta were not able to capture pregnancy tests as these are claims data sources and not medical records.

Only few or no records of pregnancy tests were detected before and after the initiation of a retinoid, except in VID. The low level of recording did not allow for trend analyses nor a proper interpretation of the impact of risk minimization. Contraceptive use could not be measured in ARS and was very low in Caserta, in PHARMO, recorded contraceptive use in retinoid users was far below 100%, in VID and BIFAP, recorded contraceptive use increased over time. In BIFAP there was a significant increase in recorded contraceptive use after 2018 RMM, but still far below 100%.

Conclusion: Pregnancy tests are not recorded in the electronic health databases, neither in medical record data sources. Contraception use at start or during a retinoid treatment, was recorded very differently across databases since several non-user/non-permanent contraceptive measures are not recorded because of lack of reimbursement or OTC status. In the Netherlands and Spain, we could investigate trends of contraceptive coverage, only in BIFAP we could observe a significant increase after 2018 RMM.

1.3 Objective 3

Aim: To determine, in so far as is possible, patients' use of effective contraception in compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for oral retinoid-containing medicinal products, by indication (i.e., acne, psoriasis and eczema), by age group, by method of contraception and by database.

Methods: An observational times series study consisting of females of childbearing age (aged 12 and 55 years) derived from electronic health record data sources in the Netherlands (PHARMO database network), Spain (Base de datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria (BIFAP); Valencia health system integrated database (VID), and Italy (ARS Tuscany), Caserta Record Linkage Database (CASERTA)), who used an oral retinoid during the study period (2010-2020). To measure effective use of contraception during retinoids, we estimated the monthly occurrence of pregnancies during and within one month after stopping retinoids using the ConcePTION pregnancy algorithm and utilizing only pregnancies with high level of certainty. Newly occurring pregnancies were aggregated pre and post intervention, and expressed as number of pregnancies per 1000 retinoid users. Pregnancies were classified by quality in the following colour code: green (high reliability, with recorded start and end date of pregnancy in the data banks), colour yellow (when the end date is recorded and start date is estimated, blue when the pregnancy start date is recorded and the end date is imputed and red with imputed start and end of pregnancy). Validation of pregnancies was conducted.

Results: In PHARMO, 41 pregnancies started during a retinoid treatment, and 20 persons started a new retinoid treatment episode during an ongoing pregnancy. Most of those occurred prior to the 2018 RMM. In the post intervention period 3 pregnancies started during the course of a retinoid treatment and 2 registered the initiation of a new retinoid treatment episode while being pregnant. In both categories of analysis, rates per 1000 retinoid users lower after the 2018 RMM.

In ARS, 19 pregnancies (8 green and 11 yellow) started during retinoid treatment, and in 9 pregnancies (1 green and 8 yellow) an oral retinoid was started while being pregnant. In both instances, rates per 1000 retinoid users decreased after the implementation of the RMM in August 2018.

In Caserta (IT), 6 pregnancies started during retinoid treatment and in 7 pregnancies the retinoid was started during pregnancy. All of those pregnancies occurred prior to the 2018 RMM.

In VID (ES), 96 pregnancies (44 green and 52 yellow) started during a period of retinoid treatment and in 100 pregnancies (22 green and 78 yellow), the retinoid was started during pregnancy. Rates in both scenarios are lower after intervention. Rate per 1000 retinoid users during pregnancy lower from 0.72 in the pre-intervention time to 0.42 in the post-intervention period; the last remains the highest rate among all DAPs. Rate per 1000 retinoid users that started a pregnancy while taking an oral retinoid decreased from 0.70 to 0.39.

In BIFAP (ES), 11 pregnancies started (yellow) during a retinoid treatment and in 12 (yellow) the retinoid was started during pregnancy. The rate of retinoid prescriptions during the course of a pregnancy decreased from 0.17/1000 retinoid users before the 2018 RMM to 0.11/1000 retinoid users after the 2018 RMM. Rate of pregnancies started while taking a retinoid doubled from 0.12/1000 retinoid users in the pre-intervention period to 0.22/1000 retinoid users in the post-intervention one.

Conclusion: Based on currently available data we observe pregnancies occurring during use of oral retinoids before and also after 2018 RMM. Verification of pregnancies confirm that pregnancies happened during retinoids, or that retinoids were started during pregnancy. Since we focused on pregnancies where a registry entry or an end date was available, we will underestimate pregnancies at the end of the follow-up period leading to a potential beneficial effect that would require to be confirmed with more follow-up time.

1.4 Objective 4

Aim: To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns over time for alternative medicines prescribed in females of childbearing potential and female becoming pregnant where oral retinoid-containing medicinal products had previously been prescribed or discontinued, by indication, age group and database, using longitudinal data collected from six electronic health care databases from different EU countries.

Methods: An observational times series study comprising females of childbearing age (aged 12 and 55 years) from the corresponding databases in the Netherlands (PHARMO), Spain (VID and BIFAP), Italy (ARS and Caserta), and Denmark (DNR), who had a recorded prescription or dispensing of an oral retinoid-containing medicinal product between 01 January 2010 and 31 December 2020. We estimated the incidence rates of alternative medication use (prescriptions/dispensing) for eczema, psoriasis and acne among oral retinoid users and the rate of switching from oral retinoid to an alternative medicine per month. We estimated the change in level and trend of switches from retinoids to alternative medications after the implementation of the 2018 PRAC intervention through an interrupted time series analysis.

Results: We found a steady trend of alternative medicines use for acne, except in the Danish registers where we observed a gradual decrease, and in VID, where alternative medicines use decreased after the last trimester of 2019 (COVID-19 pandemic period). Alternative medication use for eczema showed an increasing trend for the Danish registers and PHARMO, but a steady use through the study period for the other databases. For psoriasis, more heterogenous patterns are found, with an increasing trend for Danish registers, PHARMO and ARS, while after 2019 it increased in Caserta and decreased in VID. The ITS analysis of switching rates from retinoids to alternative medicines before versus after the 2018 RMMs revealed that there was a non-statistically significant change in level nor trend for PHARMO, and ARS. For Caserta, VID and BIFAP, a statistically significant decrease in slope trend of switchers was observed. However, this change disappears when excluding the COVID-19 pandemic period from the model. For the Danish register, it was not possible to model the ITS analysis because there were not enough time points after the 2018 RMMs.

Conclusion: A seasonal pattern of alternative medication consumption was seen for acne especially in ARS and VID, and for psoriasis in DNR. When comparing retinoid switching to alternative medications before and after the 2018 RMM, no significant changes were seen for any of the countries involved.

1.5 Abstract Objective 5

Aim: To draw conclusions on the effectiveness of the 2018 EU RMMs for retinoids.

Methods: Evidence generated from Objectives 1-4, weighed by the strengths and limitations of the analyses, was used to draw conclusions on the effectiveness of the RMMs, per country and across European countries included in the study. Pregnancies were classified by quality of the underlying information to estimate the start and end date in green (recorded end and start date), yellow (recorded end date and imputed start date), blue (recorded start date imputed end date) and red (both start and end date imputed).

Results: We found no change in oral retinoid use after the 2018 RMMs in any of the data sources (Objective 1), and only a slight increasing trend in recorded contraceptive measures in BIFAP and VID (Objective 2). In each of the data sources pregnancies occurred during retinoid treatment before and after the RMM, there is a delay in detection of pregnancies, as often they need to finish before being recorded, which may artificially lower the post-intervention rates. Furthermore, we observed no change in switching rates from retinoids to alternative medications (Objective 4). Noteworthy, these findings should be interpreted in context of the limitations that we faced, such as an inability to investigate some objectives due to limited data availability on pregnancy test or over-the-counter use of some contraceptives, and the occurrence of COVID-19 pandemic, which has shortened and impacted our post-intervention period and limited our ability to run ITS analyses for some objectives and some databases.

Conclusion: Based on the above findings on various objectives in this study, we can conclude that there was very limited measurable impact of the 2018 RMM on oral retinoid use and the pregnancy prevention measures among women of childbearing age in our included databases. Moreover, pregnancies still seem to happen during oral retinoid treatment after the implementation and with the focus on pregnancies with certainty of happening (yellow/green), that were also validated.

2. Abbreviations

AEMPS - Agencia Española de Medicamentos y Productos Sanitarios, Madrid, Spain
ARS - Agenzia Regionale di Sanità della Toscana, Italy
BIFAP - Base de datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria
CDM - Common Data Model
DAP - Data Access Partner.
DNR - Danish National Registers
EMA - European Medicines Agency
EU - European Union
FICF - Fundació Institut Català de Farmacologia, Barcelona, Spain
FISABIO-HSRU - The Foundation for the Promotion of Health and Biomedical Research of Valencia Region
- Health Services Research Unit
ITSA - Interrupted Time Series Analysis
LSHTM - London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, UK
MPP - monthly period prevalence
PC - Primary care
PHARMO - The PHARMO Database Network, The Netherlands
PRAC - The Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee
RMM - Risk Minimisation Measures
SmPC - Summary of Product Characteristics
UMCU - University Medical Center Utrecht, The Netherlands
UU - Utrecht University, The Netherlands
VID - The Valencia health system integrated database

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Name	Role
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5. Milestones

Milestone	Planned date	Actual date	Comments
Preliminary study plan	25 Apr 2019		
Study protocol	12 Jul 2019		
Start of data collection	July 2020		The month in which data extraction for some centres started. Data collection is a part of routine practice (clinical, administrative, surveillance), and has been ongoing since before 2010 in all data sources.
End of data collection	September 2020	December 2020	The month in which data extraction for some centres ended.
Study report	25 Dec 2021	28 Mar 2022	Extension was granted. Analysis of the full DNR data, as stated in the original protocol (V1.0) was not possible due to delayed data access.
Manuscripts	25 Feb 2022	30 Mar 2022	Extension was granted. Analysis of the full DNR data, as stated in the original protocol (V1.0) was not possible due to delayed data access.
Update of study report	April 15, 2022	Oct 31, 2022	Update of the report

6. Rationale and background

Retinoids are vitamin A derivatives that regulate cell differentiation, proliferation, and apoptosis; they are used to treat dermatological conditions such as severe acne (isotretinoin), psoriasis (acitretin) and eczema (alitretinoin); some retinoids are also used to treat skin manifestations of T-cell lymphoma (bexarotene) and acute promyelocytic leukaemia (tretinoin) (Balack 2018). Retinoids bind to nuclear receptors that belong to the large family of steroid hormone receptors (Sbidian et al 2011). Retinoids modulate many types of proteins, including epidermal proteins, metalloproteinases, and cytokines (Sbidian et al 2011).

All retinoids are established as highly teratogenic and must not be used during pregnancy, due to a risk of irreversible, disrupting, and sometimes life-threatening consequences. Retinoic acid embryopathy includes central nervous system abnormalities (hydrocephalus, microcephaly), external ear abnormalities (anotia, microtia, or absent external auditory meatus), cardiovascular abnormalities (septal wall and aortic defects), facial dysmorphism (cleft palate), eye abnormalities (microphthalmia), thymus gland and bone abnormalities (Lipson et al 1993). Human data on congenital malformations after oral retinoid exposure shows a significant risk of retinoid embryopathy (in up to 30% of foetuses exposed); furthermore, it is known that approximately one-third of pregnant patients will undergo spontaneous abortions. Because of this, pregnancy is an absolute contraindication for all oral retinoids in the EU (EMA retinoid summary of product characteristics; PRAC Referral under Article 31 of Directive 2001/83/EC) and elsewhere.

If a pregnancy occurs in a treated woman, treatment should be discontinued and the patient should be referred to a doctor specialized (or experienced) in teratology for evaluation and advice. If pregnancy occurs after stopping treatment, there is a risk of serious malformation of the foetus. This risk persists until the product has been completely eliminated, which is within a month (three years in acitretin's case) after the end of the treatment (EMA retinoid summary of product characteristics).

In 2003, a pregnancy prevention program (PPP) was implemented in the European Union (EU) for oral retinoids. The effectiveness of this PPP has been reviewed and, despite a reduction in number, pregnancies exposed to retinoids have continued to occur, raising concerns about compliance and effectiveness of PPPs in clinical practice (Crijns et al 2012, Henry et al 2016, Raguideau et al 2015, Teichert et al 2010). In addition, periodic safety update reports have shown limitations regarding the extent of the warnings and the risk minimisation measures in place for women of childbearing age (Schaefer et al 2010, Dathe et al 2018). In June 2018, a referral procedure resulting from pharmacovigilance data confirmed the known teratogenic risks of retinoids and their persistent exposure in pregnant women (Zomerdijk et al 2014), the Pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee (PRAC) required harmonisation of warnings about the teratogenic risk (PRAC Referral under Article 31 of Directive 2001/83/EC), and asked for a post-authorisation safety study to assess the effectiveness of updated risk minimisation measures in women of childbearing age for oral retinoids (acitretin, alitretinoin and isotretinoin), after the introduction of the PPP in the EU. According to the 2018 measures by PRAC (EMA Updated measures for pregnancy prevention during retinoid use), oral retinoids are contraindicated in women of childbearing potential for all indications (acne, eczema and psoriasis) unless the conditions of a PPP, which has to be implemented in all EU Member States, are fulfilled. Some publications suggest that, despite successive modifications, the PPPs in Europe, as in the rest of the world, continue to be insufficient (Kovitwanichkanont et al 2018), although there are certain limitations when monitoring the effectiveness of these types of measures (Charlton et al 2018).

To account for differing healthcare systems in the EU, the implementation of specific elements of the PPP (updated in March 2018) were to be considered and agreed at national level (see **Box 1**).

This study has been developed under the Framework service contract (nr. EMA/2018/28/PE). The objective of this study is to investigate the use of oral retinoid-containing medicinal products authorised in the EU before and after implementation of the 2018 revised measures for pregnancy prevention in clinical practice, and effectiveness of the 2018 intervention, using longitudinal data collected in six electronic health care databases from four EU countries.

Box 1. Summarized measures established in the 2018 Pregnancy Prevention Programme (PPP)

Summarized measures of the 2018 PPP
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• There is strict contraindication in pregnancy, so all the measures described are focused on achieving this aim.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Signature of the pregnancy risk awareness form by the patient at the start of treatment
<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Monthly visits
<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ 30-day prescription requirement
<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ 7 day-prescription validity
<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Two forms of contraception
<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Medically supervised pregnancy testing
<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Educational materials
<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Visual reminder (boxed warning / pictogram / symbol)

7. Research question and objectives

The main research question of this study was, “What was the effect of the EU label changes and the revised pregnancy prevention programme (2018) on utilisation of retinoid-containing medicinal products and to what extent did prescribers and patients comply with recommendations?”. To answer this, we completed the following objectives:

Objective 1

To determine drug utilisation and prescription patterns of retinoid-containing medicinal products in females of childbearing potential, and to investigate whether significant changes in prescribing patterns occurred (pre-/post-intervention).

Objective 2

To determine prescribers’ compliance with the recommendations in the SmPC for retinoid-containing medicinal products, by indication (i.e., dermatological conditions including acne, psoriasis and eczema), by age group, by duration of use, by and database.

Objective 3

To determine, in so far as is possible, patients’ use of effective contraception in compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for oral retinoid-containing medicinal products, by indication (i.e., acne, psoriasis and eczema), by age group, by method of contraception and by database.

Objective 4

To determine drug utilization and prescription patterns over time for alternative medicines prescribed in females of childbearing potential and females becoming pregnant where oral retinoid-containing medicinal products had previously been prescribed or discontinued, by indication, by age group and by database.

Objective 5

Based on the results of the above, to estimate the effectiveness of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for oral retinoids.

8. Amendments and updates to the report

Date	Amendment	Justification	Report section
May 9, 2022	incidence is first ever during period, restriction of pregnancies to those with green/yellow code, inclusion of aggregate counts to avoid masking of small cell numbers analysis of information on pregnancies and update of ITS on sensitivity analyses	Comments of EMA	Results
Oct 31, 2022	study population updated for Denmark.	Need of update based on most recent analysis script.	Results
Oct 31, 2022	Figure 14c. updated	Need of correction.	Results

9. Research methods

9.1. Study design

The study design for the different objectives is a time series study, where outcomes (drug utilization, pregnancy prevention measures, pregnancy) are assessed every month. An interrupted time series analysis (ITSA) has been conducted for hypothesis testing.

9.2. Study population

The study was conducted in childbearing potential females (age 12-55 years) between 01 January 2010 and 31 December 2020 (see **Figure 1** below).

- Subjects may be excluded during initial data processing if they meet the general exclusion criteria. This will help to reduce data volume. DAPs may apply these exclusion criteria during their ETL, but they must report this (it will also be detected when assessing at patient flow). Subjects with any record of male sex will be excluded.
- Time series of cross-sectional analyses is performed over this period (monthly analyses). The final month will begin December 1st 2020.

Figure 1. Schematic of data coverage and definition of study population

9.3. Setting and data sources

Data from six sources were included: Netherlands (sample, nationally representative), Denmark (national), Italy regional databases (Tuscany and Campania) and Spain (multiple regions, and regional Valencia), covering more than 80 million source population (approximate estimate: 15-20 million childbearing age females).

Table 1 Overview of databases used in this study

Characteristic	PHARMO Nationally representative	Danish National Registries*	ARS Tuscany	BIFAP Multi-regional	FISABIO Valencia	Caserta Campania
Data access provider	PHARMO	University of Copenhagen	ARS	AEMPS	FICF/FISABIO	University Messina
Country (pop. size in million)	Netherlands (17.0)	Denmark (5.8)	Italy (59.8)	Spain (46.5)	Spain (46.5)	Italy (59.8)
Type of database	EMR	ADM	ADM	EMR	EMR	ADM
# in DB	4.2 million (prior to linkage)	5.8 million	3.6 million	9 million	5.1 million	0.9 million
GP Rx	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Outpatient Rx spec.	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Private Rx	No	No	No	No	No	No
Inpatient hospital Rx	Yes (not utilised in this study)	No	No	No	No	No
Date of Rx	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Date of Dispensing	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Quantity	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Duration	Yes	Yes	Based on DDD	Yes	Yes	Based on DDD
Coding of drugs	ATC	ATC	ATC	ATC	ATC	ATC
Dosing regimen	Yes	No	no	Yes	Yes	No
Oral contraceptives	Yes	Yes	No	Yes (only those dispensed with a prescription)	Yes (only those publicly funded)	No
Duration calculation	Yes	DDD based	No	Yes	Yes	no
Observed pregnancy test dx	No	No	No	No	Unclear for retinoids	Unclear for retinoids
Date fitted IUD	Yes	Date of prescription fill (not copper IUD)	No	No	No	No
Date removed IUD	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
Written record of OC advise	Free text potentially	No	No	Free text potentially	No	No
Hysterectomy	Yes*	Yes	Yes	If recorded by GP	Yes	Yes
Oophorectomy	Yes*	Yes	Yes	If recorded by GP	Yes	Yes
Sterilization	Yes*	Yes	Yes	If recorded by GP	Yes	Yes
Partner vasectomy	No	No	No	Not	No	No
Completed Menopause	Free text potentially	No	No	If recorded by the GP and Free text potentially	No	No
Reasons for stopping Retinoid	No	No	No	From EMR, Free text potentially	No	No
Coding of disease	ICPC, ICD-9, ICD-10, *	ICD-10	ICD-9 CM/ICD-10	ICD-9, SNOMED, ICD-10	ICD-9CM/ICD-10CM	ICD-9CM
Pregnancy outcomes	Linkage to birth register	Linkage to birth register	Linkage to birth register /interruption registry/spontaneous abortions registry	Mother's records if recorded by the GP and in hospital discharge record	Linkage to perinatal registry	Mother's records

ADM = Administrative; ATC = Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical; EMR = Electronic Medical Records; ICD= International Classification of Disease, ICPC = International Classification of Primary Care. DDD=defined daily dose

* Due to data access delays for the Danish National Registers, diagnosis, procedure and pregnancy information is not available during the study; only information on prescriptions will be available

Spain: FISABIO

The region of Valencia, with 5 million inhabitants, is part of the Spanish National Health System, a universal public healthcare system. Information will be obtained from the population-based electronic information systems of the Valencia Health Agency (VHA) and the regional Government of Valencia: (1) The Population Information System (SIP) provides an identification number for each person under Valencian Health Service (VHS) coverage, and registers some demographic characteristics, and dates and causes of VHA discharge, including death. (2) The Minimum Basic Dataset (MBDS) at hospital discharge is a synopsis of clinical and administrative information on all hospital discharges, including diagnoses and procedures (all electronic health systems in the VHS use the ICD-9-CM). (3) The Emergency Department module (ED) including ED dates of visit and discharge and reason for discharge. (4) The electronic medical record (EMR) for ambulatory care, available in all primary healthcare centers and other ambulatory settings. It has all the information on patients regarding diagnoses, their personal and family medical history, laboratory results, lifestyle, etc. (5) The pharmaceutical module (prescription information system), part of EMR, includes information about both physician prescriptions and dispensations from pharmacy claims. (6) The Corporate Resource Catalogue (CRC) provides information about the geographical and functional organization of VHS, its health centers, health services provided and professionals in healthcare. Specific public health registries are available and linkable at an individual level (such as the perinatal registry and the congenital anomalies registry, from

which pregnancy outcomes can be obtained) All the information in these systems can be linked at an individual level through the SIP number.

Spain: BIFAP

BIFAP (Base de Datos para la Investigación Farmacoepidemiológica en Atención Primaria), a computerized database of medical records of primary care (www.bifap.aemps.es) is a non-profit research project funded by the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Medical Devices (AEMPS). The project started in 2001 and currently includes clinical information of 14,810 physicians (General Practitioners (GPs) and pediatricians). Nine participant Autonomous Region send their data to BIFAP every year. BIFAP database currently includes anonymized clinical and prescription/dispensing data from around 14 million (9.4 active population) patients representing 85% of all patients of those regions participating in the database, and 29% of the Spanish population. Mean duration of follow-up in the database is 8.7 years. Information collected by PCPs includes administrative, socio-demographic, lifestyle, and other general data, clinical diagnosis and health problems, results of diagnostic procedures, interventions, and prescriptions/dispensations. Diagnoses are classified according to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC)-2, ICD-9CM and SNOMEDCT system, and a variable proportion of clinical information is registered in "medical notes" in free text fields in the EMR. Additionally, information on hospital discharge diagnoses coded in ICD-10 terminology is linked to patients included in BIFAP for a subset of periods and regions participating in the database. All information on prescriptions of medicines by the PCP is incorporated and linked by the PCP to a health problem (episode of care), and information on the dispensation of medicines at pharmacies is extracted from the e-prescription system that is widely implemented in Spain BIFAP does not overlap with FISABIO. A mother-child linkage has not been made so far and no private/specialist prescribing is available.

Netherlands: PHARMO Database Network & Netherlands Perinatal Registry

The PHARMO Database Network is a population-based network of electronic healthcare databases and combines data from different primary and secondary healthcare settings in the Netherlands. These different data sources, including data from general practices, in- and out-patient pharmacies, clinical laboratories, hospitals, the cancer registry, pathology registry and perinatal registry, are linked on a patient level through validated algorithms. Detailed information on the methodology and the validation of the used record linkage method can be found elsewhere (van Herk-Sukel et al 2010).

The longitudinal nature of the PHARMO Database Network system enables to follow-up more than 4 million (25%) residents of a well-defined population in the Netherlands for an average of ten years. Data collection period, catchment area and overlap between data sources differ. Therefore, the final cohort size for any study will depend on the data sources included. As data sources are linked on an annual basis, the average lag time of the data is one year. All electronic patient records in the PHARMO Database Network include information on age, sex, socioeconomic status and mortality. Other available information depends on the data source. To address the objectives of the present study the following PHARMO databases will be used: General Practitioner Database, Out-patient Pharmacy Database and Pregnancy Register.

The General Practitioner (GP) Database comprises data from electronic patient records registered by GPs. The records include information on diagnoses and symptoms, laboratory test results, referrals to specialists and healthcare product/drug prescriptions. The prescription records include information on type of product, prescription date, strength, dosage regimen, quantity, and route of administration. Drug prescriptions are coded according to the WHO Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System. Diagnoses and symptoms are coded according to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC), which can be mapped to ICD codes, but can also be entered as free text.

The Out-patient Pharmacy Database comprises GP or specialist prescribed healthcare products dispensed by the out-patient pharmacy. The dispensing records include information on type of product, date, strength, dosage regimen, quantity, route of administration, prescriber specialty and costs. Drug dispensings are coded according to the WHO Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System. Oral contraceptives are mostly prescribed by GPs, but can also be obtained directly in the pharmacy, this will be captured in PHARMO as was proven before (Bezemer et al 2016, Goossen et al 2017). PHARMO is listed under the ENCePP resources database (www.encepp.eu/encepp/resourcesDatabase.jsp).

The Netherlands Perinatal Registry is maintained by Perined and comprises data on pregnancies, births and neonatal outcomes of births in the Netherlands, voluntarily collected by perinatal caregivers, mainly for benchmarking. Records include information on mothers (e.g. maternal age, obstetric history, parity), pregnancy (e.g. mode of conception, mode of delivery) and children (e.g. birth weight, gestational age, Apgar score). Diagnoses and symptoms are coded according to the Perinatal Registry code lists. For more information: www.perined.nl. For research purposes the data can be linked with the PHARMO Database Network via a trusted third party (TTP). Permission on a project basis is needed from PHARMO as well as Perined to obtain these data. Combined Out-patient Pharmacy and data from the Netherlands Perinatal Registry currently cover a catchment area representing 0.5 million residents for the data cut up to 2015 (to be updated). Additional linkages to the other PHARMO databases can be performed on a patient-level. Data collection period, catchment area and overlap between data sources differ. Therefore, the final cohort size for any study will depend on the data sources included.

Denmark: Danish National Registries

Denmark has a tax-funded health care system ensuring easy and equal access to health care for all its citizens, and all contacts with the system are recorded in administrative and medical registers. The records carry a unique personal identification number, called the CPR-number, assigned to every Danish citizen. Linkage between registers at an individual level is possible because this CPR-number is used in all Danish registers. All registers have a nationwide coverage and an almost 100% capture of contacts covering information on currently 5.8 million inhabitants plus historical information. For the purpose of the study, we will obtain information from the following registries. The Danish National Prescription Registry (DNR) includes data on all drugs dispensed from Danish pharmacies from 1995 and onwards, including dispensing date, Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) code, product code and amount. Sociodemographic data is available from the Danish Civil Registration System, such as gender, date of birth, migration, vital status and civil status recorded since 1968. The Medical Birth Register captures pregnancies ending in a live birth and data on stillbirth. The Patient Register contains diagnoses from hospitalisation and contacts to hospital outpatient clinics that can also be used as a proxy for the indication (Kildemoes et al 2011, Bliddal et al 2018).

Italy: Caserta claims database

The Caserta database is an administrative claims database containing patient-level data from the city of Caserta, in the Campania region. The coverage of these databases in the respective catchment areas is very high because they consist of Italian National Health Service (NHS) data and practically all the persons living in the catchment areas are NHS beneficiaries. The databases therefore contain data related to healthcare claims covered by the NHS, covering a wide variety of healthcare services.

The data in Caserta accounts for approximately 15% of the Campania regional population. This database has been previously used in multi-database projects with other databases where harmonized methods were applied to Caserta database. Catchment area population from 2005-2017 in Caserta consists of 907,410 persons. The Caserta linkage databases consists of several databases which are linked through a unique patient identifier: a demographic registry, containing demographic patient information as well as first and last date of contact with National Health Service (NHS), out-patient pharmacy claims database with information on concerning all dispensed drugs reimbursed by the Italian NHS, as well as hospital discharge diagnose databases, emergency department admissions database, claims for diagnostic and laboratory tests ordered, and a registry of patients exempt from reasons for healthcare service co-payment exemptions (e.g. diabetes mellitus, dementia, and other chronic diseases), emergency department visit diagnoses and diagnostic tests. Patient level data from this claim database, including other drugs reimbursed by the NHS and dispensed by community pharmacies, can be linked together, using a unique patient identifier.

Italy: ARS database

The Italian National Healthcare System is organized at regional level: the national government sets standards of assistance and a tax-based funding for each region, and regional governments are responsible to provide to all their inhabitants. Tuscany is an Italian region, with around 3.6 million inhabitants. The Agenzia regionale di sanità della Toscana (ARS) is a research institute of the Tuscany Region. ARS' database comprises all the tables that are collected by the Tuscany Region to account for the healthcare delivered to its inhabitants. Moreover, ARS collects tables from regional initiatives. All the tables in the ARS' data source

can be linked with each other at the individual level, through an pseudonymous identifier. ARS' database routinely collects primary care and secondary care prescriptions of drugs for outpatient use, and is able to link them at the individual level with hospital admissions, admissions to emergency care, records of exemptions from copayment, dispensing of diagnostic tests and procedures, causes of death, mental health services registry, birth registry, spontaneous abortion registry, induced terminations registry. A pathology registry is available, mostly recorded in free text, but with morphology and topographic Snomed codes. Mother-child linkage is possible through the birth registry.

9.4. Study variables

Lists of medicine, diagnostic, regional procedure and other medical observation codes, as well as codes generated by processing free text information can be found in **Annex 5**.

9.4.1. Exposure definition

The exposure of main interest for the whole study are oral retinoid containing medicinal products: acitretin (D05BB02), alitretinoin (D11AH04) and isotretinoin (D10BA01).

Additionally, exposure to oral contraceptives, intrauterine devices, vaginal rings, contraceptive patches, and contraceptive injections was retrieved for assessment of appropriate contraception. Exposure to folic acid supplements was used for ascertainment of pregnancy wish.

Exposure to antidepressant medications was used as part of the algorithm employed in ascertainment of depression.

Operationalization for all drug exposures

Drugs were extracted from the drug files by ATC code and/or product name. A list of authorized medicinal products and their ATC codes is attached in **Annex 5**.

Treatment initiation for all drug exposures

Treatment initiation was defined as the date of the first record of the specific (ATC level) prescription or dispensing in the follow-up period. When both prescription and dispensing dates were available, the dispensing date was used.

Duration of retinoid treatment

Duration was defined as the number of days of therapy from initiation to discontinuation of therapy. Since duration is often not provided, it was derived. The theoretical duration of each prescription was estimated based on the DAP specific method. For example, this was based on the number of units prescribed/dispensed and the dosage regimen (prescribed daily dose), or, when information on dosage regimen is missing, based on either the typical period for prescribing medicines for chronic diseases in the country (e.g., 30 or 7 days) or the duration based on the assumption that one defined daily dose (DDD) will be used per day. The date based on the start of the prescription/dispensing plus the estimated duration of the dispensing/prescription was considered the end date of the drug. If the start of a next prescription of the same drug (same ATC code) fell during treatment duration of the prior prescription/dispensing, we considered this as the start of that prescription.

ARS: 30-day fixed duration of retinoid per dispensing

BIFAP used a multistep algorithm:

1. First step, if there is a duration (dot) written by the doctor and there is also enough data to calculate the duration* (this means that there are both, the written duration and the calculated duration) the shorter

duration of these two is chosen. For example: if the physician wrote a duration of 35 days but the dispensed amount is 30 tablets and the posology is 3 tablets/day, the calculated duration is 10 days. 10 days is the shortest duration, so this is chosen *Duration is calculated as number of dispensed units in a package divided by the number of units taken each day (posology=presc_quantity_per_day); If posology is not issued by the doctor this is calculated as number of dispensed units in the package divided by the duration.

2. Second Step: if there is only one duration (written or calculated) this is the duration that applies.

3. Third step: if there isn't any duration, the distance between prescriptions is used. This distance must be in the pre-calculated range of the durations for this product.

4. Fourth step: If none of the above steps could be achieved, then the mode or the median (it is a researcher choice) of the prescription duration is set (mode or median are calculated at the product level, from those prescriptions with written or calculated duration available)

5. If none of the above is possible, the prescription duration is considered as missing value. Missing values were imputed with a value of 30 days.

CASERTA used an algorithm based on the following algorithm: Calculate days of treatment = number of boxes dispensed * coverage per box If number of boxes dispensed is missing, set number of boxes dispensed == 1. Coverage per box was retrieved from an external data table. Missing values were imputed with a value of 30 days.

DANISH NATIONAL REGISTERS used a 90 day fixed duration of retinoid per dispensing

FISABIO/FICF (VID) used the prescribed duration. Missing values were imputed with a value of 30 days.

PHARMO used an algorithm based on standardized macros from the PHARMO database network. These macros utilize dispensing and product information to estimate the duration of an individual dispensed medicine. Missing values were imputed with a value of 30 days.

Retinoid treatment discontinuation

Patients not receiving any other prescription or dispensing of the same drug (same ATC code) within 90 days after the calculated end date, with at least these days of follow-up, were considered as discontinuers (a sensitivity analysis was conducted with 30 days).

Incidence and prevalence of use

Retinoid users were included in calculation of incident use if no prescription or dispensing for the same drug was recorded in the one year prior to that prescription/dispensing. Retinoid users were included in calculation of prevalent use during a period if one or more days of a prescription duration fell within the period of interest.

Switching of retinoid to alternative medications and concomitant use of alternative medications

Switching of retinoids to alternative medication was defined as the discontinuation of the specific retinoid (see definition above) and the incident use of an alternative medication during the last prescription of the retinoid or after discontinuation as defined above (See **Figure 2**).

Concomitant use of alternative medication was defined as use of a medication (any day of overlap) during a retinoid prescription, if not classified as a switch.

Figure 2 Scenarios of switching to an alternative medication. In each scenario, use of the alternative medication is incident (no use in the prior year)

9.4.2. Alternative medications

Alternative prescribed medicines for treatment of eczema were defined as: emollients, topical or oral steroids, calcineurin inhibitors (cyclosporine, pimecrolimus, tacrolimus), and PDE4 inhibitors (crisaborole), phototherapy (UVB), biologicals (e.g.dupilumab), keratolytics, methotrexate.

Alternative prescribed medicines for treatment of psoriasis were defined as: Topical: emollients, corticosteroids, vitamin D analogs (calcipotriene, calcitriol), tazarotene, calcineurin inhibitors (ciclosporin), anthralin, pimecrolimus, tacrolimus, apremilast, biological agents (etanercept, infliximab, adalimumab, ustekinumab, secukinumab, ixekizumab, brodalumab, guselkumab, tildrakizumab, certolizumab pegol), dimethyl fumarate

Alternative prescribed medicines for treatment of acne are defined as: topical retinoids, azelaic acid, topical antimicrobials (benzoyl peroxide, erythromycin, nadifloxacin, and clindamycin, sulfacetamide, dapsone), oral antibiotics (doxycycline, minocycline, and tetracycline), macrolides, hormonal therapy.

9.4.3. Outcomes

Reason for discontinuation (Objective 1)

The reason for discontinuation was assessed by electronic medical records and categorized as pregnancy wish (folic acid use), pregnancy, adverse reactions, multiple or unknown during the 90 days preceding discontinuation. Reasons for discontinuation was based on coded information.

The default reason for discontinuation was unknown. If we could measure within the follow-up time any of the other events (see below), this was the reason for discontinuation, if multiple criteria apply these were counted.

Reasons for a composite discontinuation were considered to be the earliest of:

- Pregnancy wish if within the 90 days following discontinuation of alitretinoin or isotretinoin a female is prescribed folic acid. A 90-day lookback window was used, instead of a longer window, to increase the specificity of this category. See **Annex 5** for ATC mapping of folic acid.
- Pregnancy was assumed as the reason for discontinuation if a pregnancy event was observed within the 90 days following discontinuation of the retinoid medicine. A 90-day lookback window was used, instead of a longer window, to increase the specificity of this category.

- Discontinuation was assumed to be for adverse reactions if a known and pre-defined retinoid-associated ADR event leading to medical attention was recorded within the 90 days following discontinuation of the retinoid medicine. A 90-day lookback window was used, instead of a longer window, to increase the specificity of this category. Causality was inferred by this temporal association. Pre-defined ADRs were obtained from the summary of product characteristics of the retinoids.

As minor events may not lead to discontinuation and not be captured in the EHR data, only adverse events (requiring medical attention) were considered. These included: depression, cardiovascular events, dermatological events, gastrointestinal events, haematological events, hepatic events, immunological events, musculoskeletal events, neurological events, otic events, ophthalmic events, psychiatric events, respiratory events, other events. See **Annex 5** for the diagnoses codes for each of these events. Because specific codes for drug ineffectiveness do not exist in the coding systems used by the data sources in this study and ineffectiveness cannot be assumed from repeated codes for drug indications, reason to discontinue because of ineffectiveness could not be assessed.

Pregnancy testing (Objective 2)

Pregnancy testing was defined as a health care professional-witnessed pregnancy test. Recorded pregnancy testing was obtained from the electronic medical records of GPs or specialists if recorded.

Recording of pregnancy testing was assessed within the window 90 days prior or 90 days after a retinoid treatment initiation. As per RMM recommendations pregnancy testing should be done within 1 day prior to treatment start and also one month after stopping treatment. For acitretin, women should undergo pregnancy test periodically with 1-3 monthly intervals for a period of 3 years after stopping treatment. We counted the number of recorded pregnancy tests per retinoid prescription. See **Annex 5** for the codes to identify pregnancy testing.

Contraceptives measures (Objective 2 & 3)

Effective contraception at each retinoid prescription and monthly after discontinuation was defined as at least one user independent method applied to the woman (permanent or non-permanent), or a hormone-based method combined with a barrier method.

Barrier methods cannot be assessed reliably from healthcare databases so were not considered. The effectiveness of contraception was therefore categorized as follows.

Non-use of contraception was defined as absence of evidence of all:

- Prescribed/dispensed hormonal contraception AND
- Permanent method AND
- User-independent non-permanent measure

Ineffective use of contraception was defined as evidence of:

- Prescribed hormonal contraception AND

Absence of evidence of:

- Permanent method AND
- User-independent non-permanent measure

Effective use of contraception was defined as evidence of:

- Permanent method OR
- User-independent non-permanent measure

Barrier, user dependent methods:

Contraceptive diaphragm or cap, male condom, female condom was not ascertainable from data sources.

Hormone based user dependent methods

Vaginal ring (21 days, one week off), contraceptive patch (weekly for 3 weeks, one week off), progestogen only pill or desogestrel progestogen-only pill (28 days continuously), combination pills (21 days one week off)

User independent non-permanent methods

Contraceptive implant (progestogen releasing: 3 years), contraceptive injection (progestogen releasing 8-13 weeks), intrauterine device (coil: 5-10 years), intrauterine system (progestogen releasing 3-5 years)

User independent permanent methods

Female sterilization and hysterectomy. Because the data sources used do not allow for family linkage, male partner sterilization (vasectomy) were not considered. All observation time following occurrence of a procedure or diagnosis code for female sterilization or hysterectomy was classified as a period of effective contraception coverage.

See **Annex 5** for ATC codes for contraceptive methods and Annex IV for mapping of codes for permanent methods

Duration of use (Objective 2)

Duration of retinoid use was defined as the time from initiation of treatment based upon the first recorded prescription or dispensing in the look-back or study periods until discontinuation. Women meeting criteria for discontinuation may re-initiate, leading to multiple episodes of treatment.

The median of retinoid treatment duration of a retinoid prescription was fixed to 30 days for all data sources after discussions with the DAPs.

Pregnancy (Objective 3)

A woman was considered to be pregnant if she reported a pregnancy to the GP/ obstetrician / dermatologist, which was confirmed by a positive pregnancy test, ultrasound, or if there was linkage to a pregnancy/birth record. To properly identify pregnancies across databases, we applied a pregnancy algorithm developed by Gini R., *et al.* within the framework of the ConcePTION project (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/>). This algorithm was built on a published algorithm for detecting pregnancies in an electronic health record database by Matcho et al 2018. Codes from the Matcho algorithm were mapped to other terminologies using the Codemapper, and tagged into categories to identify beginning/end or outcomes of pregnancy by Carlos Durán. These were further reviewed and finetuned by the DAPs and the working group, and fed into the algorithm that was developed. The strategy for defining and validating pregnancies using disparate electronic information is described in **Annex 4a**, and a list of codes used by some data sources to identify pregnancies is found in **Annex 4b**.

Briefly, the proposed pregnancy algorithm allowed the identification of past and ongoing pregnancies from 4 main streams: perinatal or birth registries, administrative data banks using diagnosis codes, European registry of congenital abnormalities (EUROCAT) and a tailored-combined stream, which uses additional data

from medical observations (item-sets). Within this framework, three of the six participating databases were able to identify pregnancies through linkage to a perinatal or birth register (PHARMO, ARS and VID). The algorithm first detects any record of live birth, stillbirth, ectopic pregnancy, abortion, or delivery. These events then represent the set of pregnancies in the data source and pregnancy start dates were assessed for each of these pregnancy outcomes using LMP, recorded gestational age, and fertility procedure, ultrasound, amniocentesis, amenorrhea, and pregnancy test dates. The ordering of quality of records is established and stored in variable `order_quality`; records are of

- quality green if both `pregnancy_start_date` and `pregnancy_end_date` are recorded.
- quality yellow if `pregnancy_end_date` is recorded as the record date and `pregnancy_start_date` is imputed.
- quality blue if `pregnancy_start_date` is recorded and `pregnancy_end_date` is imputed.
- quality red if both `pregnancy_start_date` and `pregnancy_end_date` are imputed.

The script can be found at <https://github.com/ARS-toscana/ConcePTIONAlgorithmPregnancies>

9.4.4. Other variables

Age groups for each objective were defined as follows:

- 12 to <21 years of age
- 21 to <31 years of age
- 31 to <41 years of age
- 41 to 55 years of age

For study baseline measurements, a female's age was defined as the year of entry into the study. For objectives 1-4, age was defined as the age at which the prescription occurs.

9.5. RMM Intervention

Although EMA released a statement on the recommendations and PPP in March 2018, the start and duration of implementation varied across regions and between products. The dates of the first and last actions in the implementation of the PPP across the regions included in this study, as gathered by the EMA, are presented below in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Implementation start and end date by country of revised Risk Minimisation Measures.

Country	Start date	End date
Netherlands	10-08-2018	12-12-2018
Denmark	16-07-2018	11-10-2018
Italy	08-08-2018	02-10-2018
Spain	24-07-2018	01-12-2018

Prescriptions were categorized as occurring pre and post intervention based upon the period during which the prescription began. Pregnancy prevention measures were already in place for retinoids prior to the 2018 revised measures (which were mostly re-enforcing educational materials), which may mitigate the measurable impact of the 2018 measures.

9.6. Strategy for distributed analyses

This study has been conducted in a distributed manner using the ConcePTION Common Data Model (CDM) and common analytics. The common data model has been described in full elsewhere (Thurin et al 2022). Federated analyses, such as in this study, have been used successfully in several other European multi-

database projects (Trifirò et al 2014). This approach was taken to support the standardisation of analyses across data sources in the study and to improve transparency of the process of evidence generation. The quality processes explained in section 9.4 and 9.5 are also strongly related to this CDM procedure.

The CDM should be able to handle rich and non-standardized data vocabularies. Thus, the ConcePTION vocabulary was based on a combination of the data banks' dictionaries: each coded column of the ConcePTION CDM comes with a corresponding column indicating its dictionary. The vocabularies of the meaning and origin columns are open: each DAP is free to include additional values, to capture the information that in their experience may be useful when processing the records for a study (Thurin et al 2022).

Figure 3 illustrates the data processing steps, going from original data, stored locally by the DAP to generation of analytical data sets on which the final analyses were run. All of the data sets described in Figure 2 remained local with the DAP, and data processing and analysis steps were performed by DAPs using common analytical scripts provided by the central statisticians. Only the results of the data quality checks and analyses were uploaded to a central, secure platform of Utrecht University.

Figure 3 Steps of the data processing between original data and the analytical dataset

The Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) process from original data to the ConcePTION CDM was assisted by an ETL standard template (see **Annex 6**) defining the link between source data (original data banks) to the target tables of the CDM. For each table and column to be populated in the CDM, the following information was collected: (i) the rule that feeds each target column based on source columns and/or context information, and (ii) the rule that generates target record(s) from each source record. All DAPs had interviews with trained members of the core team before filling the ETL, where they mapped out general information about their available contents and tables; during the template filling process, to help and clarify doubts; and a last short interview to check whether there were any errors. This way, it was aimed to prevent from potential issues or adaptations needed before the script conversion execution. During the quality check process (see Section 9.4), the design of the ETL process underwent multiple rounds of revision by each DAP, until DAPs and the central statisticians were satisfied that the ETL process was of high quality. The mapping of data to a CDM then permitted common analysis scripts to be run to process the data stored locally and generate analysis results.

All analyses scripts are open source and are publicly available at: <https://github.com/LOT4/LOT4STUDIES>.

9.7. Data analysis

9.7.1. Analysis of Demographics and Baseline Characteristics

The source population and study population from each database were described in numbers and person-time by age, and calendar year. Retinoid users were described in terms of baseline characteristics (first prescription/ dispensing in follow-up) with the following variables: age, indication, incident/ prevalent, concomitant use of alternative treatments (prescribed before and lasting until first retinoid prescription/dispensing). Frequency tables were generated for categorical variables. The proportion of missing data for each variable was reported as well as the proportion of treatment episodes estimated using population averages, per country.

9.7.2. Statistical methods

Interrupted time series analysis

To test the effect of the 2018 risk minimization measures on outcomes, interrupted time-series analyses (ITS) were conducted. Segmented generalised least squares regression analysis were used to compare the pre-intervention (2010-2018) and the post-intervention (2018-2020) estimates in each of the tested outcomes (see **Table 2** for specific RMM implementation dates per country): i) incident and prevalent retinoid use per month year, ii) incidence of pregnancy testing compliant prescriptions, iii) incidence of contraception non-compliant (ineffective contraception) prescriptions, and iv) treatment discontinuation in retinoid users, v) switches from retinoids to alternative medications per month year. The precise timing of intervention was defined as the month in which EMA interventions were implemented in each country (described in Section 9.3 Intervention). For the main analyses, a slope and level-change model with two segments was considered: segment 1 models constant pre-intervention outcome levels, segment 2 models post-intervention outcomes. Implementation periods were excluded from the analysis following countries' implementation times: 5 months in the Netherlands, 4 months in Spain and 2 months in Italy. Trend changes were tested using a time*intervention period interaction term (Bernal et al 2016).

Pre-/post-intervention change was tested with the level and trend change. Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation of RMM and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention incidence/prevalence estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention. Regression coefficients, confidence intervals and p-values were estimated. Incidence rate ratios for tested outcomes i-v were calculated for the post vs. pre-intervention period using the same generalised least squares regression models. For all main analyses, data was used from January 1st 2010 until the last date of available information.

Key assumptions of the generalised least squares regression models were tested. First-order autocorrelation was tested with the Durbin-Watson statistic and graphically with autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation function plots (Durbin et al 1950). Autoregressive structures were modelled to account for autocorrelation, where necessary.

The beta coefficients produced from ITS analyses of each objective were presented separately per country. We originally planned to conduct pooled analyses on the output of ITS analyses for various objectives and per each data source, by using a one-stage meta-analysis. However, due to substantial heterogeneity in retinoid use and data capture between data sources, leading often to heterogeneity in the results from different data sources, pooling was not possible and was therefore not conducted.

9.7.3. Statistical analyses

Objective 1: Utilization patterns

Monthly incidence rates of retinoid use were estimated as the number of first ever new retinoid users in a given month (no use in year prior) divided by the number of person-years of follow-up in that quarter. Calculations were stratified by age categories, indication and database (in annex 9).

Monthly period prevalence estimates (MPP) were estimated and defined as the number of female retinoid users of childbearing age during a calendar month (with at least one day of use overlapping that month), divided by the total number of females-of-childbearing-age-years of the calendar month. Generalized least squares regression was used to estimate the 95% confidence intervals around the prevalence.

ITS analyses were conducted to compare i) the monthly prevalence of retinoid use and ii) monthly incidence rate of retinoid use before and after the period of intervention (as described in Section 9.7.2), stratified by database.

To assess discontinuation, the frequency of discontinuation divided by number of retinoid users in the previous quarter were calculated by database, age group, duration of therapy and reason for discontinuation (adverse drug reaction, pregnancy, pregnancy wish, unknown).

ITS analyses were conducted to compare the monthly incidence of retinoid discontinuations (Numerator comprises discontinuers in females who used retinoids in the prior month (denominator)) before and after the period of intervention stratified by database and indication.

Objective 2: Compliance of prescribers

Compliance of prescribers with recommendations for retinoid containing medicinal products were analysed on a prescription level (each retinoid prescription) and assessed by analysing contraceptive coverage and pregnancy testing confirmed by healthcare professional before retinoid prescription and monthly during use.

First, incidence of witnessed pregnancy testing in periods before and after the intervention were calculated for women of childbearing age using person-time in women of childbearing age as the denominator.

Second, the proportions of retinoid prescriptions/dispensing with a physician-confirmed and recorded pregnancy test up to 90 days prior to the date of prescription or dispensing, and ii) until 90 days after the start of the retinoid prescription/dispensing. The denominator was the total number of retinoid episodes in each corresponding month. An ITS analysis was planned but was unable to be modelled due to low numbers, therefore was not conducted. Third, to establish whether prescribers were compliant with recommendations for contraception, we calculated the proportion of retinoid prescriptions/dispensing that were prescribed a contraception method 90 days before the start of a retinoid treatment episode. The denominator was the total number of retinoids each corresponding month. Furthermore, the proportion of retinoid prescriptions/dispensing that occurred within a period of contraception coverage was assessed. The latter was stratified by database and age.

ITS analyses were planned to test for a change in the proportion of effectively compliant (during a period of effective contraception coverage,) and ineffectively compliant (during a period of ineffective contraception coverage) retinoid prescriptions after the intervention, with time points per quarter year, however very few data sources had adequate information on type of contraceptive, so we were not able to conduct it.

Objective 3: Compliance with contraceptive use

The monthly incidence of pregnancies in the study population of females of childbearing potential was calculated over the study period, stratified by database, this may be considered as background rate. The numerator was the number of new pregnancies, and denominator the number of females during follow-up in that month. The occurrence of a pregnancy event during a retinoid exposure have been assessed in two ways. First, we counted the monthly occurrence of a retinoid prescription/ dispensing during a pregnancy time window, as medication use during pregnancy. For this, we only counted the first date of a retinoid prescription/ dispensing and removed any other prescription/ dispensing dates to avoid duplicate counting of events during the same pregnancy for each unique patient. Second, we counted the monthly occurrence of start of a pregnancy during a treatment episode of retinoid. For this, we did not remove multiple potential pregnancies that might have occurred in the same patient during a (long) treatment with an oral retinoid, as each could represent the teratogenic risk to a unique foetus. For both sub-objectives, we produced rates per number of prevalent users of retinoids each month, and also aggregated counts and rates per each year and for the whole study period before and after the 2018 RMMs, per each database. Rate differences for aggregated counts of pregnancies per 1000 users were calculated using Episheet 2015 risk data formula's comparing post-intervention frequency by pre-intervention frequency.

Objective 4: Alternative medicines

The rate and switching to an alternative medication were calculated in the following manner. The monthly incidence of treatment switches was estimated as the number of switches (use of alternative medications) divided by the number of prevalent retinoid users and discontinuers each month. ITS analyses were conducted to test for a level or trend change in switches & concomitant use of alternative medications after the intervention. Incidence rates of switches to alternative medications in the post vs. pre-intervention period were compared by using the generalized least squares regression models developed for the ITS analysis.

Objective 5: Effectiveness of risk minimization

An overall assessment of the effectiveness of the 2018 risk minimization measures was made based on the results of the analyses within objectives 1-4. Descriptive findings were interpreted in accordance with the

definition of appropriate and inappropriate use according to the CMDh (21 March 2018), as far as possible given the data available within the included databases.

The intervention was determined to be effective if there is no pregnancy during use of retinoids and within one month after the 2018 RM.

9.7.4 Missing data

Since the underlying data represent attended medical care, we generally assumed that absence of information of clinical events means absence of that condition. No imputation was done for missing data.

9.7.5 Sensitivity analyses

Sensitivity analyses were conducted on the definitions of effective contraception and the definition of discontinuation.

The following sensitivity analyses were conducted in addition to the main analyses:

- Objectives 1,4: The discontinuation period for gaps between retinoid prescriptions for the definitions of switching and discontinuation were reduced from 90 to 30 days.
- Objectives 1,4: The study period will be restricted to end at February 2020, to investigate the impact of excluding the period of time affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which is known to have impacted on health care seeking behaviour and collection of prescriptions. This sensitivity analyses are presented in the main results alongside with the main analysis.

The sensitivity analyses were conducted individually and not in combination.

9.8. Quality management

This study bears an ENCePP Seal and is registered in the EU PAS register (EUPAS31095). The study was conducted according to the guidelines for Good Pharmacoepidemiology Practice (GPP) (International Society for Pharmacoepidemiology 2008) and according to the ENCePP code of conduct (European Medicines Agency 2018). All data access providers had experience in conducting pharmaco-epidemiological research and research was done by researchers trained in pharmacoepidemiology. All programs were programmed according to agreed coding standards and were validated by double programming or source code review with second programmer involvement. Only validated software (R and/or SAS version 9.4, SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC) was used for statistical analyses.

The members of the consortium had similar local quality assurance systems in place. In addition, several quality and transparency assurance measures have been taken and maintained in the consortium across the centres, such as adherence to the ENCePP code of conduct and acquiring of the ENCePP Seal, development of protocols according the ENCePP guidance, registration of protocols at the ENCePP registry of studies, sharing and comparison of program codes across centres, documentation of harmonisation of coding systems across multiple datasets (exposure, outcome, confounder definitions), and blinded conduct of studies. Study protocols were peer-reviewed by an advisor (at least one member of the consortium that was not leading nor actively participating in the study). Regarding conflict of interest, a declaration of conflict of interest from the principal investigators or co-investigators have been presented to the Steering Committee.

Aggregated data on a monthly level was sent to and stored on YODA, an Utrecht University's institutional research data repository, registered at RE3DATA.org. YODA complies with Utrecht University's information security policy for data classified as public, internal use or sensitive. All YODA data is stored in at least two geographically spread locations. The data is stored and transmitted in an encrypted format. All researchers who needed access to YODA were trained and monitored by the data management group.

9.9. Checking of data quality

The final study dataset and statistical programs used have been archived and stored on a secured, access limited computer driver locally. All data remained local and only summary measures were inspected in

collaboration with the core team at the Utrecht University/UMC Utrecht (UU/UMCU). Please, see **Annexes 4 and 5** for the specific ATC and medical observation codes used.

We applied the level 1-3 checks that have been developed as part of the Quality Framework in the IMI-Conception project. All checks are available on the ConcePTION GitHub with explanations and R-code.

Level 1 quality checks assess the completeness and content of each variable in each table to ensure that the required variables contain data and conform to the formats specified by the CDM specifications (e.g., data types, variable lengths, formats, acceptable values, etc.). This check was conducted to verify that the extract, transform, and load (ETL) procedure to convert from source data to the CDM had been completed as expected. Missingness of core compulsory variables such as date of birth or sex and formats for all values were assessed and compared to a list of acceptable formats. Graphs and frequency tables of variables with finite allowable values were created to identify unacceptable values. Counts of codes for events and exposures of interest in each data source were tabulated. The scripts for this level and instructions for running can be found publicly in the following link: [<https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/Level-1-checks>].

Level 2 quality checks assessed the logical relationship and integrity of data values within or between variables and tables. At this stage, we checked for internal consistency, to verify, for example, that all health encounters had occurred on or after an individual's date of birth. The scripts for this level and instructions for running can be found publicly in the following link: [<https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/Level-2-checks>].

Level 3 quality checks examined data distributions and trends over time by DAP database (by examining output by year and year/month). For example, a level 3 data check was to ensure that there is no large, unexpected increase or decrease in records, cuts or peaks over time. In this check, we calculated person-time in women of child-bearing potential by calendar year and database. We also calculated incidence of oral retinoid prescriptions by calendar year, database and indication, as well as incidence of various events diagnoses by calendar year and database. By comparing these types of summary measures put in context over time, anomalies and errors which can be corrected in partnership with data sources have become apparent. The scripts for this level and instructions for running can be found publicly in the following link: [<https://github.com/IMI-ConcePTION/Level-3-checks>].

The core team has developed two separate quality check sheets, the "summarised" and the "comprehensive/approval form" for each of the Level 1-3 data checks, to help with evaluating the output of these checks. The quality check sheet templates are attached as **Annex 7**. The forms have been developed to assess the output of Level 1-3 checks in a short, efficient and pragmatic way, from programming as well as pharmaco-epidemiological and clinical perspectives. DAPs uploaded the output of the Level 1-3 checks on YODA, where the core team (at UU/UMCU) could review based on the above forms. All DAPs were also invited to review the output of their data quality checks by means of these forms, and any issues or questions regarding the quality checks were discussed in 1-1 meetings with the core team. In case of any issues with ETL of data, quality of data, or running the scripts, the core team provided programming support to the DAP. There were usually several such meetings, organised in a weekly manner, to resolve any quality issues with data for each DAP, and this process has been continued until resolving of all the issues and questions.

10. Results

This section starts with our findings in the quality control process and benchmarking, which informed us about the availability of various parameters from each data source for conducting the main, secondary and sensitivity analyses. Then, the main results are reported for each objective. All detailed results (including subgroup and sensitivity analysis) for each objective and for each DAP are available as csv files in **Annex 9**.

10.1. Data quality checking and benchmarking

In addition to the data quality checks after the ETL process with the ConcePTION CDM, the core team has also checked the output of the preliminary and main analyses from all DAPs. To do this, we ran an internal and an external validation of the baseline tables and counts and rates of all key study parameters. The internal validation was performed according to the known information on the individual database, size of the study population for each DAP, availability of specific study parameters in each database, and previous information collected during the Level 1-3 data checks in the previous step. The external validation benefited from a “benchmarking sheet” with some global, regional and country-level information on incidence or prevalence rates of all key study parameters, produced by the core team after a thorough review of existing data in literature.

For the purposes of results checking at this stage, the core team has developed two separate checklists, one to review the produced output of the preliminary and main analyses by each DAP, to see if there is any major or minor output missing or if there is any unexpected value produced. The second checklist aimed to evaluate the produced counts and rates from each DAP and to compare them with the benchmarking values that was already collected in the benchmarking sheet. **Annex 8** shows the combined template review form, benchmarking checklist and benchmarking sheet that were used for internal and external validation of the study results. DAPs uploaded the analyses output on YODA, where the core team could access and review the output. DAPs were consulted about any issues that arose in weekly 1-1 meetings with them. The goal was to discuss any issues or errors that DAPs faced when running the scripts, or to detect and fix any bug or inaccuracy in the script of the common analytics, and to rerun the analyses at each centre level. This process was iterated until all the found issues were resolved, and there was a good sense of trust in internal and external validity of the produced output by taking into consideration the specific limitations of data and database at each centre.

The important aim of the two processes of “data quality checking” and “results checking and benchmarking” was to collect detailed information on the availability of various types of data from the included heterogeneous data sources in this study. This information was crucial in determining to which analyses in different objectives each data source could contribute to. **Table 3** lists a summary of this information, which served as the basis for the main and stratified analyses in this study. As seen in **Table 3**, the data available for this study from the Danish National Registers was limited due to access delays, which prevented access to birth information, diagnostic or procedural information from the registers. The Danish data available for this study came from another study with similar purpose of studying the impact of risk minimisation measures on drug utilisation including contraceptives and some oral retinoids. The sample included only users of contraceptives and information on some but not all oral retinoids and alternatives to the study medications. Therefore, in order to estimate rates of utilisation and other events, external population-level data was used to provide approximate numbers of the total eligible Danish persons in the study, to be used as a denominator in several analyses.

Table 3 A summary of the contributions of each database to the ITSA, based on the findings of data availability, preliminary results checking and benchmarking.

Analysis	Danish National registries, DK	ARS Tuscany, IT	PHARMO, NL	BIFAP, ES	CASERTA, IT	VID, ES
Objective 1: retinoid utilisation and discontinuation	Included in the analysis. <i>Could not provide diagnosis codes for this study No data on folic acid since this is OTC and not reimbursed</i>	Included in the analysis. Diagnosis codes are only from hospital which is not the setting where indications and ADRs may not present.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.
Objective 2a: pregnancy tests	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Pregnancy tests not captured.</i>	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Pregnancy tests not captured.</i>	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Excluded from the analysis <i>Pregnancy tests not captured.</i>	Included in the analysis
Objective 2b: contraception	Included in the analysis. Incomplete data on all type of contraceptive use	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Contraception insufficiently captured to analyse.</i>	Excluded from the analysis. <i>Contraception insufficiently captured to analyse.</i>	Included in the analysis Incomplete data on all type of contraceptive use	Included in the analysis Incomplete data on all type of contraceptive use	Included in the analysis Incomplete data on all type of contraceptive use
Objective 3: pregnancy	Excluded from the analysis. <i>No available data on pregnancies.</i>	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis	Included in the analysis.
Objective 4: alternative medications	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.
Objective 5: Effectiveness of RMM	Excluded from the analysis. <i>No available data on pregnancies.</i>	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.	Included in the analysis.

10.2. Description of the Study Population

10.2.1. Study Objective 1

A total of 10,714,182 women of childbearing age from the six involved DAPs were included in the study population. **Table 4** describes the baseline characteristics of the study population by database. The median follow-up time was 7.6 years for Danish registries (data available only until 2018), 8.2 years for ARS Tuscany, 9.9 years for Caserta, 10.0 years for PHARMO database, 9.4 years for BIFAP, and 11.0 years for VID in Spain. Mean age of the study population at start of follow-up ranged from 29.7 [IQR 13.3 years] in PHARMO to 33.8 [IQR 13.3 years] in ARS); the most frequent age group for all data sources was from 41 to 55 years, except for PHARMO, where 12-21 years old persons had highest frequency of all categories.

Table 4 Baseline characteristics of the study population (women of childbearing age) within the different databases in Denmark, Italy, Netherlands, and Spain (for Objective 1).

Country, and total active population in data source	Denmark, National registries	Italy, ARS - Tuscany	Italy, Caserta	Netherlands, PHARMO	Spain, BIFAP	Spain, VID Valencia	
Size of the population (females 12-55 years of age), N	1,575,216	1,117,251	319,962	591,500	5,066,393	2,043,860	
Median follow-up, years (IQR)	7.6 (3.9)	8.2 (6.8)	9.9 (5.1)	10.0 (2.4)	9.4 (6.4)	11 (6)	
Mean age at start of follow-up date, years (SD)	30.8 (13.0)	33.8 (13.3)	31.5 (13.5)	29.8 (13.3)	31.7 (13)	31.4 (13.2)	
Study population, number (%) by age category	12- <21 years	306,370 (19.4)	244,952 (21.9)	88,126 (27.5)	188,176 (31.8)	1,212,120 (23.9)	531,492 (26.0)
	21- <31 years	315,625 (20.0)	181,458 (16.2)	60,946 (19.0)	121,343 (20.5)	1,107,176 (21.9)	419,315 (20.5)
	31- <41 years	372,708 (23.7)	279,584 (25.0)	71,955 (22.5)	121,455 (20.5)	1,272,723 (25.1)	498,517 (24.5)
	41-55 years	580,513 (36.9)	411,257 (36.8)	98,935 (31.0)	160,526 (27.1)	1,474,374 (29.0)	594,536 (29.0)

Abbreviations: SD: standard deviation

10.2.2. Study Objectives 2, 3, and 4

A total of 88,992 women of childbearing age used an oral retinoid at any time during the study period January 1, 2010 - December 31st, 2020. **Table 5** describes the baseline characteristics of this population by data source. Mean age at start of follow-up in the study ranged between 18.9 [IQR 8.5 years] for Caserta to 22.2 [IQR 11.1 years] for ARS). For each data source, the majority of the retinoid users were in the younger age groups 12-21 years of age at start of follow-up, and around 20 percent was in the 21-31 category, with decreasing percentages to higher age categories. Age could have been older at the moment of use.

Table 5 Baseline characteristics of persons using oral retinoid during follow-up in the different databases in Denmark, Italy, Netherlands and Spain (for Objectives 2, 3 & 4).

Country and total number of women in childbearing age using retinoids	Denmark, National registries	Italy, ARS - Tuscany	Italy, Caserta	Netherlands, PHARMO	Spain, BIFAP	Spain, VID Valencia	
Female oral retinoid users, 12-55 years of age, N	40,834	6,930	5,565	4,225	15,981	15,457	
Mean age at start of follow-up, years (SD)	21.4 (9)	22.2 (11.1)	18.9 (8.5)	21.4 (10.6)	21.4 (10.6)	20.3 (10.2)	
Oral retinoid users, number (%) by age category at start of follow-up	12- <21 years	24,552 (60.1)	4,105 (59.2)	3,971 (71.4)	2,535 (60.0)	9519 (59.6)	10,071 (65.2)
	21- <31 years	9,407 (23.0)	1,358 (19.6)	1,023 (18.4)	859 (20.3)	3436 (21.5)	2,866 (18.5)
	31- <41 years	4,810 (11.8)	715 (10.3)	337 (6.1)	479 (11.3)	1659 (10.4)	1,399 (9.1)
	41-55 years	2065 (5.0)	752 (10.9)	234 (4.2)	352 (8.3)	1367 (9.0)	1,121 (7.3)

Abbreviations: SD: standard deviation

10.3. Main results

10.3.1. Objective 1 – utilisation of oral retinoids

Figures 4 and 5 show the monthly incidence (new users per 1000 persons per month [PM]) and monthly prevalence (per 1000 PM) rates of oral retinoid users. The dashed lines show the timing of the 2018 RMM implementation. The study period was shortened for Danish registers and for PHARMO, which means that less post-intervention time is available. In Caserta, data differed between 2010 and 2015, which means that for ITS analyses, we only include data from 2015. All data sources show a distinct seasonal pattern with a decrease in the incidence of new treatments with oral retinoids during the summer months. Results of stratified analyses are provided in csv tables in **Annex 9**.

Most of the incidence rates of new oral retinoid use in women of childbearing age were (far) below 1 new user per 1000 PM. Overall incidence rates of new users of any of the three retinoids over the study period were 0.22/1000 PM in DNR (DK), 0.06/1000 PM in PHARMO (NL), 0.16/1000 PM in Caserta (IT), 0.06/1000 PM in ARS (IT), 0.07/1000 PM in VID (ES) and 0.03 new users per /1000 persons per month in BIFAP (SP). The lowest incidence rate of oral retinoid prescriptions was observed in BIFAP. VID in Spain also had low rates of dispensing of oral retinoids, but higher than prescription data from BIFAP; VID captures medicine dispensing which are prescriptions from GPs and specialists whereas BIFAP captures prescriptions by GPs and progressively over time dispensings (table 1). Seasonality was pronounced in southern countries and less so in the Netherlands (see Figure 4).

Figure 4 Incidence rates of oral retinoid dispensing or prescription in women of childbearing age over the study period in the participating data sources.

Figure 4 (continued) Incidence rates of oral retinoid dispensing or prescription in women of childbearing age over the study period in the participating data sources.
The time of implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for retinoids is shown with a dashed line. Note that the study period differs per data source.

Figure 5 Monthly prevalence rates of oral retinoid use (dispensed or prescribed) in women of childbearing age during the study period in the participating data sources

Figure 5 (continued) Monthly prevalence rates of oral retinoid use (dispensed or prescribed) in women of childbearing age during the study period in the participating data sources
 Rates are given per 1000-persons per month. The end of study period may vary between centres. The time of implementation of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for retinoids is shown with a dashed line.

10.3.2. Objective 1 – Changes in the incidence and prevalence rate of oral retinoids after intervention as well as discontinuation

Incidence and prevalence of oral retinoid use

Figure 6 shows the results of the ITS analyses on prevalence and incidence rates of oral retinoid across the entire study period, by censoring before the SARS-Cov-2 pandemic period and by restricting to 2015-02/2020 (pre-2015 was quite different data capture in several data sources). We found no statistically significant level or trend change in incidence or prevalence of retinoid prescriptions/dispensing in women of childbearing age after the 2018 EU RMM intervention as compared to the period before in any of the data sources.

We could not model the ITS for the Danish registries since there were not enough data points available after the 2018 risk minimisation measures for this data source. Incidence pre-intervention was 0.22/1000 PM, and post-intervention 0.26/1000 PM.

In PHARMO, the Netherlands monthly prevalence of oral retinoid use in women of childbearing age increased over calendar time, but no significant change was seen in level and trend after (as compared to before) the implementation of the 2018 RMM measures (figure 6a). This was the same for incidence rates and after restriction to the period from 2015 onwards. Incidence pre-intervention was 0.06/1000 PM, and post-intervention 0.09/1000 PM.

In ARS Tuscany (IT) (figure 6b), monthly prevalence of oral retinoid use in women of childbearing age increased over calendar time, but no significant change in level or trend was seen after (as compared to before) the implementation of the 2018 RMM measures. For incidence rates of new users, any significant increase was seen immediately after the policy intervention (level change) and over time (trend change) in both, the analysis running from January 2010 to December 2020 and in the analysis censoring the months of the SARS-Cov-2 pandemic. Overall incidence in the main analysis pre-intervention was 0.05 new users per 1000 PM, and post-intervention 0.09 new users per 1000 PM, including the Covid-19 period in 2020. Annex 9 provides monthly data with age stratification.

In Caserta (IT) (figure 6c), the 2018 RMM resulted in a significant trend change (increase) for prevalent retinoid users. This finding was not confirmed when the analysis was censored at February 2020 (excluding the Covid-19 months March to December, 2020). For the incidence rate, level and trend changes were not significant after the implementation of the 2018 RMM, neither in the main analysis (2015-december 2020) nor when excluding the Covid-19 months. Incidence pre-intervention was 0.14/1000 PM, and post-

intervention 0.24/1000 PM, including the Covid-19 period in 2020. Annex 9 provides monthly data with age stratification.

In VID (ES) (figure 6d), the ITS analysis for prevalent and incident users did not show any significant level or trend change after the 2018 RMM in both, the main and the sensitivity analysis. Incidence of new users of retinoids pre-intervention was 0.06/1000 PM, and post-intervention 0.09/1000 PM, excluding the Covid-19 period. Annex 9 provides monthly data with age stratification.

In BIFAP (ES) (figure 6e), trends of incidence and prevalence retinoid users show a stable pattern over the 11-study years. RMM in 2018 did not result in a significant change in incidence or prevalence figures, neither immediately after the implementation (level) nor over time (trend). These findings were consistent when the analysis truncated the Covid-19 months in 2020. Incidence pre-intervention was 0.03/1000 PM, and post-intervention rate was 0.02/1000 PM. Annex 9 provides monthly data with age stratification.

PHARMO, The Netherlands

Figure 6a PHARMO. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on prevalence and incidence rates of retinoid use in female subjects of childbearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2020 (or until availability, or 2015-2020).

Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention incidence/prevalence estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention.

ARS, Tuscany (Italy)

Figure 6b ARS. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on prevalence and incidence rates of retinoid use in female subjects of childbearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2020 (or until availability, or 2015-2020).

Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention incidence/prevalence estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention.

Caserta region, Italy

Figure 6c Caserta. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on prevalence and incidence rates of retinoid use in female subjects of child bearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2020 (or until availability, or 2015-2020).

Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention incidence/prevalence estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention. For Caserta data are displayed for 2010-2020 but ITS analysis was restricted to 2015-2020 because of change in data capturing.

VID, Valencia region (Spain)

Figure 6d VID. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on prevalence and incidence rates of retinoid use in female subjects of childbearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2020 (or until availability, or 2015-2020).

Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention incidence/prevalence estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention.

BIFAP, several regions, Spain

Figure 6e BIFAP. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on prevalence and incidence rates of retinoid use in female subjects of child bearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2020 (or until availability, or 2015-2020).

Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention incidence/prevalence estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention.

Incidence by indication

Figure 7 shows the incidence of retinoid use per indication. Isotretinoin had the highest incidence of use, whereas acitretin and alitretinoin had lowest incidence. Most of the DAPs did not show a significant change in level or trend following the introduction of the RMM in 2018. In ARS (IT), RMM in 2018 produced a significant downward trend in the incidence of acitretin new users (Psoriasis).

PHARMO, The Netherlands

Figure 7a PHARMO. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on incidence rates of retinoid use for acne, eczema and psoriasis in female subjects of childbearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2019 (or until availability, or 2015-2010).

ARS, Italy

Figure 7b ARS Tuscany (IT). Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on incidence rates of retinoid use for acne and psoriasis in female subjects of childbearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2020.

*Due to the lack to data points over time, an interrupted time series analysis on incidence of alitretinoin users for eczema was not possible to perform and therefore, it is not presented in this figure.

Caserta region, Italy

Figure 7c VID (ES). Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on incidence rates of retinoid use for acne in female subjects of childbearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2019 (or until availability, or 2015-2020).

*Due to the lack to data points over time, an interrupted time series analysis on incidence of alitretinoin users for eczema and acitretin users for psoriasis was not possible to perform and therefore, it is not presented in this figure.

VID, Spain*

Figure 7d VID (ES). Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on incidence rates of retinoid use for acne and psoriasis in female subjects of childbearing potential per database during entire study period 2010-2019 (or until availability, or 2015-2010).

*Due to the lack to data points over time, an interrupted time series analysis on incidence of alitretinoin users for eczema was not possible to perform and therefore, it is not presented in this figure.

Discontinuation of retinoids

Reasons for discontinuation were mostly (>95%) unknown (discontinuation without a recorded ADR, folic acid prescription/dispensing or a recorded start of pregnancy).

Figure 8 shows the percentage of retinoid discontinuers per month. Percentages varied across data sources from 1.9% in VID (ES) in January 2010 to 39.0% in Caserta (IT) in July 2017. Due to seasonality, most data sources presented a higher discontinuation rate during summer months (higher than 15% per month in VID, ARS and BIFAP and higher than 30% in Caserta). In PHARMO (NL) and DNR (DK), the discontinuation rate was below 10% across the whole time period. For DNR, we could not compare post-intervention discontinuation rates with pre-intervention discontinuation rates since follow-up ended in 2018.

The pre-intervention monthly retinoid discontinuation rate in PHARMO (NL) was 7.0% and the post-intervention one was 7.5%. ARS (IT) showed a pre-intervention average discontinuation rate of 16.2% and 15.9% in the post-intervention period. In Caserta (IT), pre-intervention monthly retinoid discontinuation rate reached 16.5% meanwhile the post-intervention rate was 15.3%. Pre- and post-intervention discontinuation percentages for VID (ES) were 10.6% and 12.1% per month, respectively. In BIFAP (ES), monthly discontinuation rates were 25.1% in the pre-intervention period and 18.5% in the post-intervention time.

Figure 9a to 9e show results from the interrupted time series analysis on monthly percentage of retinoid discontinuers over time. This analysis was not performed in Danish data due to the lack of data in the post-intervention period.

In PHARMO (NL) (figure 9a), neither the main nor the sensitivity analysis censoring the first 5 years of the series showed a significant change in level or trend after the implementation of the RRM in August 2018. In ARS Tuscany (IT) (figure 9b), both main and sensitivity analyses did not show a significant estimate immediately after the policy implementation (level change) as well as any change in the percentage of discontinuers over time (trend change). In Caserta (IT) (figure 9c), 2018 RMM did not produce significant level and trend changes in the percentage of monthly retinoid discontinuers.

In VID data (ES), the main analysis (2010-2020) (Figure 9d) resulted in a significant upward trend after the implementation of the RMM in 2018. This result was not consistently maintained when censoring the Covid-19 period from February to December 2020.

Finally, in BIFAP (ES), main and sensitivity analyses (Figure 9e) showed a non-significant effect of the 2018 RMMs, both in level and trend.

Figure 8 (continued). Monthly percentages of oral retinoid discontinuation in women of childbearing age during the study period in the participating data sources.

The numerator is the number of subjects who discontinue an oral retinoid that month and the denominator is number of current users the same month. The end of study period may vary between centres. Dashed lines indicate the date of the RMM implementation in every country.

PHARMO, The Netherlands, ITSA on discontinuation rates of retinoids

Figure 9a (PHARMO). Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly percentage of oral retinoids discontinuers per database during the entire and sensitivity periods.

ARS, Tuscany (Italy) Discontinuation rates of retinoids

Figure 9b (ARS). Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly percentage of oral retinoids discontinuers per database during the entire and sensitivity periods.

Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention.

Caserta region, Italy Discontinuation rates of retinoids

Figure 9c (Caserta). Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly percentage of oral retinoids discontinuers per database during the entire and sensitivity periods.

VID, Valencia region (Spain) Discontinuation rates of retinoids

Figure 9d (VID). Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly percentage of oral retinoids discontinuers per database during the entire and sensitivity periods.

Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention.

BIFAP, several regions, Spain Discontinuation rates of retinoids

Figure 9e (BIFAP). Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly percentage of oral retinoids discontinuers per database during the entire and sensitivity periods.

Level change shows the impact of the RMM implementation by measuring the distance between the projection of the slope from the period prior to implementation and the starting point of the slope directly after the implementation. Trend change measures the difference between the points of the observed real post-intervention estimates and the predicted estimates based on projection of the slope prior to the intervention.

10.3.3. Objective 2 – pregnancy testing and contraception

10.3.3.1 Pregnancy test

Danish registries, PHARMO, ARS and Caserta were not able to capture pregnancy tests. In BIFAP hardly any pregnancy test was identified (see **Annex 9**).

In VID (ES) the average monthly rate of recorded pregnancy test prior to a dispensing/prescription of a retinoid that month was 5.3% between 2015 and implementation of the RMM 2018 and 4.7% thereafter.

Due to the low rate of recorded pregnancy testing we could not model trend in the proportion of oral retinoid prescriptions or dispensing with an adherent pregnancy test before or after with an ITS analysis was not possible.

10.3.3.2 Contraceptive use

The ability to identify information on contraceptive use was limited (see **Tables 1** and **3**), since oral contraceptives and barrier methods are not always reimbursed and may not be captured in claims data. Other methods for contraception were non-user dependent (injectables/IUD) and permanent contraception (sterilization/vasectomy), these are captured in data sources. The proportion of retinoid prescriptions alongside which a contraceptive method was prescribed/dispensed (within 90 days prior to the date of prescription) was calculated per month, in addition, we calculated the monthly proportion of retinoid prescriptions that occurred during a recorded episode of contraception (as defined in 9.4)

In PHARMO, recorded prescriptions/procedures of any contraceptive within 90 days prior to retinoid use varied between 3.6-20% over time (9.8% mean over the study period) and the rate of recorded ongoing contraceptive episodes was between 10 and 20% after 2015, before 2015 there were large changes. The ITS analysis on the percentage of retinoid prescription/dispensing while using a contraceptive method did not show a change in the level nor in the trend after the 2018 RMM (see figure 14a)

Figure 10 Percentage of retinoid user with prescription within 90 days prior to retinoid prescription or during contraceptive episode in PHARMO

In ARS (IT) contraceptive use could not be assessed.

In Caserta (IT), the percentages of recorded contraceptive prescriptions within 90 days prior to a retinoid dispensing was very low, as well as the percentage of women with a recorded contraceptive use episode when retinoids were dispensed (Figure 11). No change in use of contraceptives was seen after 2018 RMM implementation (ITS analysis not conducted).

Figure 11 Percentage of retinoid user with prescription within 90 days prior to retinoid prescription or during contraceptive episode for Caserta

In VID the percentages of recorded contraceptive prescriptions within 90 days prior to a retinoid dispensing was gradually increasing over time as well as the percentage of women with a recorded contraceptive use episode when retinoids were dispensed (Figure 12). The ITS analysis showed no significant change after 2018 RMM implementation in either of the two measures (see figure 14b and 14d) when the COVID-19 months were excluded.

Figure 12 Percentage of retinoid user with prescription within 90 days prior to retinoid prescription or during contraceptive episode for VID

In BIFAP the percentages of recorded contraceptive prescriptions within 90 days prior to a retinoid dispensing was gradually increasing over time as well as the percentage of women with a recorded contraceptive use episode when retinoids were dispensed (Figure 13). The increase continued after 2018 RMM implementation. The ITS showed a significant increase in use of contraceptive measures after the 2018 RMM (see figures 14c and 14e)

Figure 13 Percentage of retinoid use with contraceptive prescription within 90 days prior to retinoid prescription or during contraceptive episode for BIFAP

ITS analysis for change in contraceptive measures before and after RMM

PHARMO, The Netherlands

Figure 14 (a). Interrupted Time Series Analysis of the percentage of retinoid prescriptions/dispensings during an episode of contraception for PHARMO (NL)

VID, Valencia region (Spain)

Figure 14 (b). Interrupted Time Series Analysis of the percentage of retinoid prescriptions/dispensing during an episode of contraception for VID, Valencia Region (ES)

BIFAP, several regions, Spain

Figure 14 (c). Interrupted Time Series Analysis of the percentage of retinoid prescriptions/dispensing during an episode of contraception for BIFAP, several regions (ES)

VID, Valencia region (Spain)

Figure 14 (d). Interrupted Time Series Analysis of the percentage of retinoid prescriptions/dispensing with any contraceptive within the 90 days before the retinoid initiation for VID, Valencia region (ES)

BIFAP, several regions, Spain

Figure 14 (e). Interrupted Time Series Analysis of the percentage of retinoid prescriptions/dispensing with any contraceptive within the 90 days before the retinoid initiation for BIFAP, several regions (ES)

Non-effective/effective contraception

Due to the lack of adequate recording of contraceptive measures we could not reliably distinguish non-effective/effective contraceptives.

10.3.4. Objective 3 - pregnancy

Excluding Denmark, in the study population (women of childbearing age), we identified 496,593 pregnancies across all databases.

Pregnancies were identified using the ConcePTION pregnancy algorithm, which outputs pregnancies with a colour of certainty; green being the highest certainty (start and end dates are registry-based), yellow being the middle certainty (end date is retrieved from the registries and the start date is imputed from it), and red being the lowest certainty (both start and end dates are imputed). Pregnancy counts presented in table 7 correspond to pregnancies categorized as green and yellow only.

In Denmark we could not observe pregnancies as they were not linked to the available data set, which just comprised population and medicines and no diagnosis codes.

In PHARMO, according to the algorithm, 41 pregnancies started during a retinoid treatment, and 20 persons started a new retinoid treatment episode during an ongoing pregnancy. Most of those occurred prior to the 2018 RMM. In the post intervention period 3 pregnancies started during the course of a retinoid treatment and 2 registered the initiation of a new retinoid treatment episode while being pregnant. In both categories of analysis, rates per 1000 retinoid users lower after the 2018 RMM (table 7). Except for one pregnancy in red, all pregnancies were green, indicating these arrive from the pregnancy register.

In ARS, 19 pregnancies (8 green and 11 yellow) started during retinoid treatment, and in 9 pregnancies (1 green and 8 yellow) an oral retinoid was started while being pregnant (table 7). In both instances, rates per 1000 retinoid users decreased after the implementation of the RMM in August 2018.

In Caserta (IT), 6 pregnancies started during retinoid treatment and in 7 pregnancies the retinoid was started during pregnancy. All of those pregnancies occurred prior to the 2018 RMM; pre-intervention rates are presented in table 7. All pregnancies identified in Caserta correspond to the yellow level of certainty.

In VID (ES), 96 pregnancies (44 green and 52 yellow) started during a period of retinoid treatment and in 100 pregnancies (22 green and 78 yellow), the retinoid was started during pregnancy, see table 7. In VID, 300 pregnancies had a lower level of certainty (red), which means that both the end and start date were imputed. These pregnancies have not been included in table 7 and are not included in the rate calculation. Rates in both scenarios are lower after intervention. Rate per 1000 retinoid users during pregnancy lower from 0.72 in the pre-intervention time to 0.42 in the post-intervention period; the last remains the highest rate among all DAPs. Rate per 1000 retinoid users that started a pregnancy while taking an oral retinoid decreased from 0.70 to 0.39.

In BIFAP (ES), 11 pregnancies started (yellow) during a retinoid treatment and in 12 (yellow) the retinoid was started during pregnancy. Red pregnancies are not included in table 7 neither in rate calculation. The rate of retinoid prescriptions during the course of a pregnancy decreased from 0.17/1000 users before the 2018 RMM to 0.11/1000 users after the 2018 RMM. Rate of pregnancies started while taking a retinoid almost doubled from 0.12/1000 users in the pre-intervention period to 0.22/1000 users in the post-intervention one, this rate increase is unique among participating DAPs (table 7).

Table 6. Aggregated concurrent pregnancy events identified as green or yellow (based on registry data) during retinoid exposure, stratified by the analytical method and by time period of pre- and post 2018 risk minimisation measures (RMM), across databases.

	A. Retinoid use during pregnancy †							B. Pregnancy during Retinoid †						
	Pre RMM			Post RMM				Pre RMM			Post RMM			
	Cases ^{&}	Users	Rate**	Cases ^{&}	Users	Rate**	RD post-pre**	Cases ^{&}	Users	Rate*	Cases ^{&}	Users	Rate**	RD post-pre**
PHARMO	18	47521	0.38	2	12893	0.16	-0.22 (-0.5 to 0.1)	38	47521	0.80	3	12893	0.23	-0.57(-0.9 to -0.2)
ARS	7	38189	0.18	2	15823	0.13	-0.05 (-0.3 to 0.2)	15	38189	0.39	4	15823	0.25	-0.14 (-0.5 to 0.2)
Caserta	7	27307	0.22	0	11677	0	-0.3 (-0.4 to -0.1)	6	27307	0.60	0	11677	0	-0.22 (-0.4 to 0)
VID	88	117247	0.75	15	36055	0.42	-0.33 (-0.6 to -0.1)	82	117247	0.69	14	36055	0.39	-0.31 (-0.6 to -0.1)
BIFAP	10	57217	0.17	2	18244	0.11	-0.06 (-0.3 to 0.1)	7	57217	0.12	4	18244	0.22	+0.10 (-0.1 to 0.3)

Analytical method A: retinoid use during a pregnancy time window

Analytical method B: pregnancy occurrence during a retinoid treatment episode

The cut-off point for a demarcation between pre- and post-intervention time periods was selected as Aug. 2018 for all DAPs, based on the implementation period of RMMs across countries. † The number of prevalent users of oral retinoids, used as the denominator for the rates here, is actually the sum of monthly prevalence counts for the time period pre 2018 RMMs and post 2018 RMMs in each database, which represent the sum of unique patients who were exposed each month to oral retinoids.

† Noteworthy, the observed concurrent events in the two analytical methods (A and B) may be overlapping.

& All pregnancies presented in this table corresponds to high (green) and yellow (middle) level of certainty. This represents pregnancies prior to validation

** per 1000

Validation of pregnancies and medicines use

Validation of pregnancies (available for ARS (IT), Caserta (IT), BIFAP (ES) and VID (ES), by manually scrutinizing the computer record), showed that the green and yellow pregnancies had high positive predictive value (PPV) of being a true pregnancy. Contraceptive use was difficult to establish even while reading through the computer files.

Table 8. Summary of findings after validation of pregnancies identified by the ConcePTION algorithm based on a manual reconciliation of the aggregated validation data

		Use of retinoid during pregnancy*				Pregnancy during retinoid treatment*			
		ARS (IT)	Caserta (IT)	VID (ES)	BIFAP (ES)	ARS (IT)	Caserta (IT)	VID (ES)	BIFAP (ES)
# Pregnancies identified by the algorithm	Green	1	0	25	0	8	0	44	0
	Yellow	8	7	78	12	11	6	52	11
	Red	14	0	190	35	6	0	110	12
# Pregnancies confirmed after validation	Green	1	0	25	NA	8	0	44	0
	Yellow	8	7	78	NA	11	4	52	8
	Red	14	0	NA	NA	6	0	NA	7

*some pregnancies can be repeated between the two categories. NA is not provided.

10.3.5. Objective 4 alternative medicines in retinoid users (switching or concomitant)

Descriptive counts and rates of alternative medicine use per various indications of retinoids (acne, eczema and psoriasis) are given in **Annex 9**.

In the Danish registers, there was a gradual decreasing trend in rates of alternative medicine use for acne (ranged between 3.32 and 8.78 per 1000 PMs), and a steady increase for eczema (ranged between 2.87 and 4.30 per 1000 PMs) and psoriasis (between 0.39 and 0.82 per 1000PMs) for the whole study period. All of them showed a seasonal pattern with lower counts in summer, especially psoriasis.

In PHARMO, rates of alternative medicines use looked steady for acne (ranged between 2.93 and 4.49 per 1000 PMs), while a small increase in trend was detected for alternative medication use for eczema (ranged between 2.33 and 4.00 per 1000 PMs) and for psoriasis (ranged between 0.21 and 0.61 per 1000 PMs) (**Annex 9**).

In ARS Tuscany, we observed a very steady trend for alternative medicines use for acne with a very evident seasonal pattern (valleys in summer months) during the whole study period (ranged between 2.72 and 10.92 per 1000 PMs), and for eczema but with less fluctuations (ranged between 3.46 and 7.34 per 1000 PMs). A slight increasing trend was observed for psoriasis alternative medication (ranged between 0.91 and 2.50 per 1000 PMs), especially from mid-year 2015 onwards (**Annex 9**).

In Caserta, acne alternative medication use showed a clear seasonal pattern but was steady through all the period (ranged between 0.02 and 10.73 per 1000 PMs) as well as for eczema (ranged between 0.08 and 9.27 per 1000 PMs). In the case of psoriasis, a gap of information registered is seen for years 2017 and 2018 (with average 0.31 per 1000 PMs) (**Annex 9**).

In VID alternative medicines for acne showed a decrease after the last trimester of 2019 (ranged between 0.10 and 0.64 per 1000 PMs) and for eczema as well (ranged between 0.08 and 0.17 per 1000 PMs), corresponding to the COVID-19 pandemic period, which pulls down the minimum rate. For psoriasis alternative medication, it had an increasing trend until the last trimester of 2017 thereafter decreasing (ranged between 0.01 and 0.08 per 1000 PMs). Seasonal fluctuations are seen mainly for acne alternative medication use (**Annex 9**).

In BIFAP, a steady use of alternative medication for acne and eczema was seen during the study period (ranged between 2.25 and 13.93 per 1000 PMs, and 3.25 and 5.51 per 1000 PMs, respectively). For psoriasis alternative medication, a decreasing was seen up to 2012 that stabilized for the period afterwards (ranged between 0.28 and 0.57 per 1000 PMs). Seasonal fluctuations are observed mainly for acne alternative medication use.

The ITS analysis of alternative medication rates including switching from retinoids to alternative medicines before versus after the 2018 RMMs revealed that there was a non-statistically significant change in level nor trend for PHARMO (**figure 14a**), and ARS (**figure 14b**). For Caserta, VID and BIFAP, a statistically significant decreasing trend in slope of alternative medicines use is seen (**figures 14c, 14d and 14e**). However, this disappeared when excluding the COVID-19 pandemic period from the model. For the Danish

register, it was not possible to model the ITS analysis because there were not enough time points after the 2018 RMMs.

PHARMO, The Netherlands

Figure 14a. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly proportion of retinoid users who switched to an alternative medication over retinoid who have not switched, numerator is the number of persons who discontinued and started use of new medicines, in female subjects of childbearing age per database

ARS Toscana, Italy

Figure 14b. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly proportion of retinoid users who switched to an alternative medication over retinoid who have not switched, numerator is the number of persons who discontinued and started use of new medicines, in female subjects of childbearing age per database

Caserta, Italy

Figure 14c. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly proportion of retinoid users who switched to an alternative medication over retinoid who have not switched, numerator is the number of persons who discontinued and started use of new medicines, in female subjects of childbearing age per database

VID, Valencia, Spain

Figure 14d. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly proportion of retinoid users who switched to an alternative medication over retinoid who have not switched, numerator is the number of persons who discontinued and started use of new medicines, in female subjects of childbearing age per database

BIFAP, multiple regions, Spain

Figure 14e. Interrupted time-series analyses (ITSA) on monthly proportion of retinoid users who switched to an alternative medication over retinoid who have not switched, numerator is the number of persons who discontinued and started use of new medicines, in female subjects of childbearing age per database

10.3.6. Objective 5: RMM effectiveness

The success of the RMM implementation was estimated by absence of pregnancies during retinoid use (from the results in Objective 3) which presents pregnancy occurring during a retinoid exposure episode and those prescriptions/dispensing of oral retinoid medicines starting during pregnancy.

A total of 88,992 retinoid users were included, and the pregnancy rates based on our algorithm per 1000 female users in childbearing age ranged between 0.1 and 0.4 per 1000 users with pregnancies still occurring after the 2018 RMM. However, the rate post-RMM may be underestimated, since registration in pregnancy registers require that the pregnancy has ended, we cannot estimate a true difference between pre- and post. A case-by-case validation of these pregnancies was conducted and showed that most yellow and greenly labelled pregnancies were confirmed and occurred during retinoid use or start.

We did not observe a change in the users of retinoids and no change in the use of contraceptive measures, alternative medication use did not change after the 2018 RMM.

The only effect we noticed was increasing contraceptive use in Spain both in VID and BIFAP, but not in other DAPs. Pregnancy tests also were hardly recorded, which may be due to the data sources rather than the physician, however it makes it difficult to monitor the effectiveness of an RMM.

11. Discussion

11.1. Key results

In this section, we summarise the main results of the study objectives. Then we put all the findings into a broader context to answer objective 5, i.e., the effectiveness of the 2018 risk minimisation measures for oral retinoid among females of childbearing age.

A total of 10,714,182 women of childbearing age from the six involved DAPs were included in the study population (12-55 years), because of different length of data availability (median follow-up time was 7.6 years for Danish registries, 8.3 years for ARS Tuscany, 9.9 years for Caserta, 10.0 years for PHARMO database, 7.8 years for BIFAP, and 11.0 years for VID in Spain. Mean age of the study population at start of follow-up ranged from 29.8 [IQR 13.3 years] in PHARMO to 33.8 [IQR 13.3 years] in ARS); the most frequent age group for all data sources was from 41 to 55 years, except for PHARMO and Danish Registers, in which 12-21 years old persons had highest frequency of all categories.

11.1.1. Objective 1: drug utilisation and prescription patterns before and after the intervention

In the study population comprising 10,714,182 women of childbearing age (12-55 years), 88,992 persons used an oral retinoid at any point during the 11 years of the study period. Most persons were below 31 years of age at start of follow-up but could be slightly older during start of retinoids. The most frequently used retinoid was isotretinoin of all users, followed by acitretin and alitretinoin. Monthly incidence and prevalence rates showed that retinoid prescriptions have a strong seasonal pattern, with decreasing incidence in the summer months, especially in southern countries. This seasonal pattern is aligned with the clinical practice recommendations to be careful with use with sunlight due to potential photosensitivity (Ferguson et al 1989), and potentially different disease severity across seasons.

Prescription/dispensing rates increased slightly over time, but comparison of the incidence or prevalence rates and trends before and after the intervention (both, excluding the COVID-19 months and on the full set of data) showed no significant change after the RMM implementation for any of the databases. To point out the existence of previous RMM measures which may lead to a non-measurable effect on all outcomes studied.

11.1.2. Objective 2: pregnancy testing and contraception in relation to retinoid prescriptions

The aim of this analysis was to assess prescribers' compliance with recommendations in the SmPC for retinoids, which require pregnancy tests and effective contraception measures before and after starting a treatment with oral retinoids.

Only few or no records of pregnancy tests were detected before and after the initiation of a retinoid, except in VID. The low level of recording did not allow for trend analyses nor a proper interpretation of the impact of risk minimization methods using this type of health care data sources.

Contraception use at start or during a retinoid treatment, was recorded very differently across databases since several non-user/non-permanent contraceptive measures are not recorded because of lack of reimbursement or OTC status. In the Netherlands and Spain, we could investigate trends of contraceptive coverage, only in BIFAP a significant increase in use of contraceptive use was shown after the 2018 RMM implementation.

11.1.3. Objective 3: pregnancy occurrence during retinoid use

The main aim of the pregnancy prevention program is to avoid pregnancies during use of retinoids. We showed that in each site, pregnancies occur also after implementation of the 2018 RMM, and

most importantly in many cases the retinoid is started during a pregnancy, which would have been detected. However, in GP data sources this start of retinoids during pregnancy may be misclassified since a first prescription could be made by a specialist. Nonetheless and even after validation of the pregnancies and exposures, we conclude that too many pregnancies (0 would be the target of the pregnancy prevention program) occur during pregnancy. The validation showed that the pregnancies identified as green or yellow have a high positive predictive value.

Based on currently available data that are based on a pregnancy algorithm and calculation of rates, we see pregnancies occurring during use of oral retinoids before and also after 2018 RMM.

11.1.4. Objective 4: drug utilization and prescription patterns over time for alternative medicines

This objective was to investigate the drug utilisation and prescription patterns of alternative medications among women of childbearing potential and pregnant women where oral retinoids had been previously prescribed or discontinued.

We found a steady trend of alternative medicines use for acne, except in the Danish registers where we observed a gradual decrease, and in VID, where alternative medicines use decreased after the last trimester of 2019 (COVID-19 pandemic period). Alternative medication use for eczema showed an increasing trend for the Danish registers and PHARMO, but a steady use through the study period for the other databases. For psoriasis, more heterogenous patterns are found, with an increasing trend for Danish registers, PHARMO and ARS, while after 2019 it increased in Caserta and decreased in VID.

The ITS analysis of switching rates from retinoids to alternative medicines before versus after the 2018 RMMs revealed that there was a non-statistically significant change in level nor trend for PHARMO, and ARS. For Caserta, VID and BIFAP, a statistically significant decrease in slope trend of switchers is seen. However, this change disappears when excluding the COVID-19 pandemic period from the model. For the Danish register, it was not possible to model the ITS analysis because there were not enough time points after the 2018 RMMs.

11.1.5. Objective 5: effectiveness of the 2018 risk minimisation measures

Based on the above findings on various objectives in this study, and taking into account that other RMMs (i.e. PPP) were in place for retinoids before 2018, we conclude that there was no real measurable impact of the 2018 RMM on oral retinoid use and the pregnancy prevention measures among women of childbearing age in our included databases nor absence of pregnancies after implementation. Given the existence of previous RMM measures, an effect may therefore not be measurable on all outcomes studied; interestingly, for all databases the period when the previous PPP was implemented is also included even not specifically analysed. This conclusion is based on limited recording of hormonal or barrier contraceptives, and the limited recording of pregnancy tests and the rates of pregnancies, which are now based on a still not validated algorithm (see Section 11.4.3).

Based on validated pregnancy data, the outcomes of pregnancy show that still too many avoidable drug exposures occur, and pregnancy rates in retinoid users vary between 0.1 and 0.4 per 1000 retinoid users, based on the pregnancy algorithm. Pregnancies also occur after 2018 RMM.

11.2. Interpretation in context of previous literature

Retinoids are vitamin A derivatives that regulate cell differentiation, proliferation, and apoptosis. Only acitretin, alitretinoin and isotretinoin are authorized in EU (EMA summary product characteristics of retinoids). Consequently, retinoids are considered to date the most serious teratogenic threat since thalidomide, and pregnancy prevention programs are implemented worldwide (eg, iPLEDGE) to reduce inadvertent exposures (Panchaud et al 2012).

Acne is estimated to affect 9.4% of the global population, making it the eighth most prevalent disease worldwide (Tan et al 2015), while eczema shows an 8%-point prevalence in northern European countries (Johansson et al 2022) and 2 to 3% total population for psoriasis (National Psoriasis Foundation [USA], Batalla et al 2018). More than 95% of our oral retinoid users were using isotretinoin, and incidence and prevalence rates did not decrease, showing that physicians did not really change their behavior after the implementation of the RMM in 2018. Alitretinoin for the indication of eczema is also prescribed for a relatively young population including women of childbearing age (Crijns et al 2012).

After the 2003 PPP was released, its effectiveness was reviewed and, despite a reduction in number, pregnancies exposed to retinoids have continued to occur (Crijns et al 2011, Raguideau et al 2015, Henry et al 2016, Teichert et al 2010). Some publications suggest that, despite successive modifications, the PPPs in Europe, as in the rest of the world, continue to be insufficient (Kovitwanichkanont et al 2018), aligned with our results. In addition, periodic safety update reports have shown limitations regarding the extent of the warnings and the risk minimisation measures in place for women of childbearing age (Schaefer et al 2010, Dathe et al 2018). We have not been able to detect step or level trend changes by comparing the periods before and after the intervention, but a generalized increasing trend in retinoids use.

A systematic review in 2011 reported that 0.2–1.0 per 1000 women of reproduction age receiving isotretinoin became pregnant and that around 75% of these pregnancies were terminated (Crijns et al 2011). Our rates are consistent, varying between 0.1-0.4 /1000. Review of studies in Europe performed so far show failures in the implementation of the 2003 PPP (Teichert et al 2010, Crijns et al 2011, Raguideau et al 2015, Henry et al 2016). Therefore, the current retinoids' PPP has to be scrutinized to identify why new measures keep having a limited impact.

Explanatory factors for pregnancy during the use of retinoids have been described as lack of contraception use in 70% of the patients and in 30%, the contraception failed (Schaefer et al 2010). A systematic review to check compliance of 2003 PPP programme in Europe (Crijns et al 2011) showed that 6-26% isotretinoin was prescribed in full accordance with the PPP. Pregnancy incidence was seen in 0.2-1.0 per 1000 women of childbearing age using isotretinoin.

11.3. Clinical and policy impact

The results of this study can hopefully inform clinicians in different specialties of the current situation of retinoid use in women of childbearing age, and give them some clues for responsible and careful prescribing of these teratogenic drugs in such a vulnerable group. Regulators may wish to consider how to more effectively implement the pregnancy prevention program. Our study also shows that it is challenging to adequately measure the impact of the additional risk minimization activities in health care data sources, which is important for monitoring purposes (Zomerdijsk et al. 2013)

11.4. Strengths and Limitations

11.4.1. Strengths related to the data source

In conducting this study, we had some strengths, partly owing to the choice of our data sources, and partly owing to the methodologies that we chose.

First, by including all women of childbearing age registered in each database at any time during the study period in addition to setting minimal exclusion criteria we mitigated an effect from selection bias. Furthermore, we included all oral retinoid containing medicinal products. Moreover, using several databases from different countries across Europe has led to a large and diverse study population with good representativeness, and generalizable results to a European setting.

The total sample size of more than 11 million female subjects of child-bearing potential permitted the calculation of precise estimates of oral retinoid utilisation and other outcomes on a monthly basis. In addition, analysis across four countries, where the 2018 RMMs were implemented in

potentially different ways (and at different moments in 2018), allowed differences in the impact of the RMMs across different counties to be examined.

Our choice of databases had each brought its own merits and advantages. Danish nationwide registers gave us the opportunity to study almost all females of childbearing age in the whole country of Denmark during the study period. The Dutch PHARMO Database Network is a unique database in the Netherlands, where one can receive the complete patient history from various linked data sources (Bezemer et al 2016). BIFAP gave us the opportunity to collect information from the Spanish National Health System with data on primary care (Maciá-Martínez et al 2020). The VID database provides exhaustive longitudinal information including sociodemographic and administrative data, clinical, pharmaceutical and healthcare utilization data from hospital care, emergency departments, specialized care (including obstetrics care), primary care and also registries of significant care areas such as congenital anomalies (García-Sempere et al 2020). The ARS Tuscany databases is a regional claims/register database in Italy with valuable information on hospitalisations, drug claims, linked data on mother and child, pathology reports and mortality. The Caserta database is an administrative claims database containing patient-level data from the region of Caserta, in the Campania region. The coverage of these databases in the respective catchment areas is very high because they consist of Italian National Health Service (NHS). Patient level data from this claim database, including other drugs reimbursed by the NHS and dispensed by community pharmacies.

11.4.2. Strengths related to methodology

A key strength of this study is the rigorous quality checking processes that were conducted. At each stage of data processing – transformation and loading to the CDM and creation of the eligible study population – rounds of review enabled any uncertainties in the data or errors in the ETL or analyses to be identified. Detailed level 1-3 checks, similar to those used by the FDA Sentinel system, ensured homogeneity and consistency in the ETL process. Any differences in the way that data were ETL'd to the CDM were seen by the investigators by comparing the outputs of the level 3 checks across data sources.

Use of the ConcePTION CDM and common analysis tools was key to minimising unwanted heterogeneity in the results due to differences in the implementation of the study. By converting all of the data sources to a standard format, it was possible to run common analysis scripts, which removed the risk of differences in the implementation of data processing steps and the analyses. By using a CDM that enforced on syntactic but not semantic harmonisation, it was possible to implement data source-specific algorithms for the definition of the duration of individual prescriptions as well as pregnancies. This allowed each DAP to use an approach that, based on their expertise with the data source, was most suitable for the research question, with the information available in the data source. The use of a common study protocol, with the use of harmonized diagnoses and drug codes and with the network having experience of conducting these types of studies, and the use of a CDM supports the interpretation and comparability of results across the selected countries, and facilitates central statistical analysis programming reducing heterogeneity between sites. Moreover, the rigorous quality checking of data sources for the particular study enhancing reliability of findings.

To evaluate the implementation and the effect of the EU communication on pregnancy prevention programme with oral retinoids, we benefited from an ITSA analysis, the strongest quasi-experimental design. This is the gold standard method for drug utilisation research with an intervention when conducting an RCT is not feasible (Grimshaw et al 2000, Been et al 2015, Jandoc et al 2015). Although the ITS design is considered the best available method to evaluate the impact of policy changes, causality cannot be established, and causal inference is subject to key assumptions.

One strength of our ITS design was the ability to extract and use many data points and observations, especially before the intervention (even after censoring the first 5 years of the series as performed in the sensitivity analysis)(Jandoc et al 2015). This helped us to reduce any effect from fluctuations, variability and outliers in medication use across the study period.

11.4.3. Limitations related to the data source

In this study we faced some limitations, either related to the data and specifications of the databases that we used, or because of the study design and methodologies that we adopted.

First of all, we have to acknowledge the absence of two data sources that we had planned for participation in the project's tender, SNIIRAM (France) and Palermo (Italy). The team in Bordeaux who was our DAP for the project did not get an estimated data delivery date from the national SNIIRAM database in spite of numerous attempts. Considering these operational issues, it was agreed to exclude the SNIIRAM data source. The Palermo database was only available from 2010 to 2017, and there were unexpected administrative/logistic difficulties in getting data from 2018-2020 due to change in personnel. It was not possible to estimate when the data beyond 2017 would be available. Therefore, it was decided to only use data from Caserta (Italy), especially since additional data sources from Italy were available.

Denmark had difficulties getting access to the Danish Register data, because of changes in access and privacy policy, they used an in-house data to participate in the study, which captured population and medicines but no diagnoses nor pregnancies. This limited the objectives to which DNR could contribute.

It should be noted that for all databases the primary aim of data collection is patient management and not medical research. No single European data source contains all the information required in this study. This had several implications for this study. As we used retrospectively collected data from electronic health records (EHRs), some common limitations when using such data, e.g., misclassification bias or confounding, may still be pertained to this study.

Misclassification of exposure might happen when there is an erroneous measurement and classification of the exposure drug among the comparison groups in a pharmaco-epidemiological study (ENCePP guide on methodological standards in pharmacoepidemiology (Revision 8)). In some databases, such as BIFAP, we had prescription and dispensing information of oral retinoids available, and in some other databases, such as PHARMO, ARS Tuscany, and Caserta, we had dispensing information of oral retinoids available. BIFAP does not capture outpatient specialist prescriptions, which may result in incomplete information on retinoids, and in a lesser extent for alternatives to oral retinoids. This was shown in the lower rates of oral retinoid use in BIFAP, as compared to VID, which showed higher rates of oral retinoid dispensing and more seasonality. Also, this may have affected the assignment of start of retinoid during pregnancy, in fact the woman may have already been on retinoids if prescribed by a specialist.

In some other databases, such as BIFAP, VID and Danish registries we could use data oral retinoid dispensing, which can help to reduce any impact from misclassification bias. Moreover, we have checked the missingness rates of various prescriptions and/or dispensing in our quality controls, as well as considering the discontinuation of retinoids, which might be due to a switch. In Spain, retinoids are widely prescribed by specialists, and BIFAP is restricted to mainly GP prescriptions, which explain the much lower rate of prescriptions than in VID. The legal status of retinoids in Spain restricts the initiation of treatment to specialist (i.e., dermatologist) supervision. General practitioners may continue retinoids prescriptions, but this practice may vary within regions.

Misclassification of exposure also concerned the recording of contraceptive measures, we observed that in many countries oral contraceptives and barrier methods were not well recorded. Limitations in historical recording may also limit accuracy of long-term methods such as hysterectomy and vasectomy or long-term implants. Another limitation was the lack of available information on over-the-counter (OTC) contraceptives, which are not captured in any of the databases. Therefore, our ability to capture oral contraceptive use (especially in Italy) was limited, and records of barrier methods were not available. This might have resulted in an underestimation of the proportion of oral retinoid use episodes that meet the criteria for adequate contraceptive coverage. However, since

the error was equal over time, it may have led to less power to detect a difference but not a differential error. Additionally, an underestimation on folic acid use consumption might be also present because its OTC dispensing; this may lead to inaccurate estimation of pregnancy wish by using this as proxy.

Another potential limitation in our study was *misclassification of outcome*. We used an adapted version of a previously validated algorithm, called "Matcho algorithm" (Matcho et al 2018). Through a series of sequential steps, this algorithm determines the date of pregnancy outcome (e.g., live birth, stillbirth, ectopic pregnancy, and abortion), and also the start date of a pregnancy episode using a hierarchy of pregnancy start markers, including last menstrual period date, gestational age record date, nuchal ultrasound record date, alpha fetoprotein test record date, and urine pregnancy record date. The wide range of codes may well capture codes related to pregnancy prevention programs, and validation of codes and pregnancies is needed to establish this. This is the reason why we limited pregnancies to green and yellow. Green being the highest certainty (start and end dates are registry-based), yellow being the middle certainty (end date is retrieved from the registries and the start date is imputed from it). This means we may underestimate pregnancies, especially at the end of follow-up since a pregnancy needs to end in order for it to be included in a registry. However, we also noted during the validation that pregnancies with a lower level certainty could have yielded to many false positives. We cannot give the exact estimate of post-RMM pregnancies without enough time allowing to pass to capture the end of the pregnancy, but can conclude they still occur. It would require longer term follow-up to validly estimate the rate.

It is also worth mentioning that acitretin, compared with other oral retinoids, has a longer teratogenic risk period after stopping exposure; thus, PPP does not recommend to get pregnant even after 3 years from acitretin's stoppage, and pregnancy tests controls are recommended to be performed for 1 year after. This extended period could not be fully captured in our study due to limited period of follow-up after 2018 RMM implementations.

The occurrence of the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic was another obstacle in conducting this research. When the time of implementation of EU risk minimisation measures for pregnancy prevention with oral retinoids use was almost the second half of 2018 in all different participating countries, the time afterwards to capture data on post-intervention period was critical. With the beginning of COVID-19 pandemic in December 2019, almost all countries went into periods of partial or full lockdown in 2020, which certainly affected not only the healthcare resources, but also access to health services, and patients' behaviour, especially their attitude towards repeated prescriptions. This has also brought us practical difficulties in accessing data from various databases, due to concurrent COVID-19 projects and slower approval and releasing of data by competent authorities. This was an issue with the Danish registries and paramount for the French data source dropping out, which was the largest data source participating. To overcome this issue, we defined some sensitivity analyses only for the COVID-19 period or some other excluding it, with the aim to have the analyses and results until the beginning of COVID-19 pandemic with estimates free of any effect from it. As an alternative to the data from Denmark originally requested, an existing data set of drug utilisation data was re-purposed to enable several analyses to still be performed.

11.4.4. Limitations related to methodology

One of the important limitations that we had in this study by using an ITSA model was not having equally spaced intervals before and after the intervention. Due to practical reasons and by design, the considered follow-up time before implementing the intervention was much longer (2010-2018) compared with the time after the intervention (2018-2020). The shorter follow-up time after the intervention has become even shorter when the COVID-19 pandemic started in December 2019, as mentioned above, making the assessments even more difficult. This might have reduced our ability to establish a sound trend in medication use in a shorter follow-up time after the intervention. However, as we used large nationwide databases and extracted several observation periods in a monthly manner, we were able to compensate this limitation to some extent.

Several methodological points need to be considered when conducting a study with an ITSA design (Jandoc et al 2015). "Autocorrelation" refers to the consecutive dependence of exposure or outcome events during the follow-up, in a way that those closer to each other are more similar than those that are further apart. "Non-stationarity" denotes to an underlying trend in the exposure or outcome event, which is unrelated to the intervention of interest, but can affect any found result from the intervention. And "seasonality" means any temporal fluctuation in the trend of medication or vaccine use, for example, which can confound the impact of intervention of interest on the trend changes. The relatively long follow-up time before implementing the intervention and our analysis model, i.e., generalized least squares regression, have helped us to identify any autocorrelation or non-stationary data among our oral retinoid users, thus minimising any impact from these on the final results. Furthermore, our exposure drug, i.e., oral retinoid, was difficult to model for the ITSA method due to a seasonal base consumption (Ferguson et al 1989), and we did not get full seasonal cycles for some of the databases, what may pull up or down the trend; this point was addressed partially in the sensitivity analysis by excluding COVID-19 period.

The other potential issue when using an ITSA model could be not having a clear intervention time point, or any possible lag period afterwards. Although the ITS design is considered the best available method to evaluate the impact of policy changes where a control group is not available, causality cannot be established. The PPP was not a clearly defined intervention. The staggered implementation across Europe made it challenging to assess the impact of the PPP on the various outcomes under study. An inability to incorporate the exact time point of the intervention in the ITS model, especially with multiple centres that had slightly different time of implementation of the intervention, could have led to mingling of pre- and post-intervention periods and flawed results. As it was not possible to fully establish precise dates of implementation in each of the countries due to variation at the regional and practice levels, we decided to model an implementation period of 6 months for the ITSA, which aimed to broadly capture the stepwise implementation. We also used a generalized least squares regression that also considered a term for the implementation period. Nonetheless, we are aware that our decision on the implementation period might have influenced the results of the ITS analysis. As another potential limitation in this study, one can think of any unmeasured time-varying confounder that has affected our outcome of interest or target population over time, especially when we did not have any control group or comparison outcome (Grimshaw et al 2000). For example, we were not aware of any major extraneous changes in societal habits or beliefs regarding pregnancy testing or contraception, nor changes in regional policies on reimbursement of pregnancy testing or contraception, over the study period. This is usually an obstacle when conducting a quasi-experimental design, such as ITSA, to study the effect of an intervention in a single study population without any comparable control group (Been et al 2015). However, stratifying our target population by age, or producing multiple results in different countries with different set of plausible unmeasured confounders and the ultimate pooling of the results (Savitz et al 2016), could have helped to reduce an effect from this.

Thus, our conclusions particularly for **Objective 5** were based on a combination of descriptive results and hypothesis testing.

12. Conclusion

Based on the above findings on various objectives in this study, we can conclude that there was a limited measurable impact of the 2018 RMM on oral retinoid use and the pregnancy prevention measures among women of childbearing age in our included databases. Moreover, pregnancies still seem to happen during oral retinoid treatment after the implementation and with the focus on pregnancies with a high certainty of happening (classified as yellow/green), that were also validated. Contraceptive use and pregnancy testing could not be reliably captured and therefore, not assessed in most of the databases. In Spain (BIFAP-ES), concurrent use of contraceptives and oral retinoids increased after the implementation of the RMMs in 2018.

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Annex 1. List of stand-alone documents

Number	Date	Title
Annex 2	15 February 2022	Explanatory guide for final results interpretation and operative summary of stratification variables by objective
Annex 3	25 February 2022	Data source-specific algorithms for study variables
Annex 4	25 February 2022	Statistical analysis plan for ascertainment of start and end of pregnancies
Annex 5	25 February 2022	List of codes (diagnosis, treatment, procedure, medical observation and processed free text) used in the study
Annex 6	25 February 2022	Extract, Transformation, Loading (ETL) conversion template for DAPs
Annex 7	23 December 2021	Quality control (level 1-3 check) sheets used for evaluating the data quality
Annex 8	25 February 2022	Review and benchmarking documents used for internal and external validation of the study results
Annex 9	11 March 2022	ZIP file containing: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Complete tables of counts and rates for each objective and data source used in the ITSA 2. Stratified analyses for each objective 3. Sensitivity analyses for each objective